

1 **Retinoic acid and TGF- β orchestrate organ-specific programs of tissue-residency**

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37

38 **Summary**

39

40 Tissue-resident memory T (T_{RM}) cells are integral to tissue immunity, persisting in diverse
41 anatomical sites where they adhere to a common transcriptional framework. How these cells
42 integrate distinct local cues to adopt the common T_{RM} cell fate remains poorly understood.
43 Here, we show that while skin T_{RM} cells strictly require TGF- β for tissue residency, those in
44 other locations utilize the metabolite retinoic acid (RA) to drive an alternative differentiation
45 pathway, directing a TGF- β -independent tissue residency program in the liver and synergizing
46 with TGF- β to drive T_{RM} cells in the small intestine. Strikingly, we found that RA was required
47 for the long-term maintenance of intestinal T_{RM} populations, in part by impeding their
48 retrograde migration. Moreover, enhanced RA signaling modulated T_{RM} cell phenotype and
49 function, a phenomenon mirrored in mice with increased microbial diversity. Together, our
50 findings reveal RA as a fundamental component of the host-environment interaction that
51 directs immunosurveillance in tissues.

52

53 **Key words**

54 T cell memory, Tissue-Resident Memory T cells, Mucosal immunity, IEL, retinoic acid

55 **Introduction**

56

57 The immune system safeguards tissue integrity, by maintaining homeostasis and countering
58 pathological and environmental challenges. Although immune cells residing in distinct organs
59 possess unique roles, they share the ability to survive long-term in local niches, ensuring proper
60 tissue function¹⁻⁴. Among tissue-dwelling immune cells, tissue-resident memory T (T_{RM}) cells
61 are specialized sentinels capable of controlling infections and malignancies, despite also being
62 implicated in triggering autoimmune diseases⁵⁻⁸. Consequently, understanding how T_{RM} cell
63 generation can be modulated is essential for developing targeted therapeutic interventions
64 across multiple disease settings.

65

66 The tissue milieu is vital in guiding T_{RM} cell development. It shapes immune cell fate,
67 phenotype and function through cytokines and metabolites that anchor immune cells in their
68 local cellular ecosystem^{9,10}. Although tissue microenvironments are diverse in nature, they
69 converge to produce molecules that enhance local retention and repress tissue-egress pathways,
70 establishing a common residency program in tissue-localizing lymphocytes¹¹⁻¹³. Transforming
71 growth factor-beta (TGF- β) is a key conductor of the program, particularly at epithelial barriers
72 where it modulates transcriptional regulators such as Eomes and T-bet¹⁴ and promotes
73 expression of adhesive molecules including CD103¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Additionally, TGF- β balances T_{RM}
74 cell proliferation, maintenance, and functionality by regulating the expression of checkpoint
75 inhibitory molecules, protecting tissues from excessive damage¹⁷.

76

77 T_{RM} cells in non-epithelial sites, such as the liver, exhibit core T_{RM} cell transcriptional
78 characteristics regulated independently of TGF- β ^{13,17}, indicating that additional organ-specific
79 promote tissue-residency. Beyond host-derived factors, recent discoveries underscored the
80 influence of commensal bacteria and their metabolites including retinoic acid (RA), secondary
81 bile acids and short-chain fatty acids in orchestrating T cell responses¹⁸⁻²⁰. The vitamin-A
82 derived metabolite RA is essential for maintaining immune tolerance by instructing CD4⁺ T
83 cell differentiation, promoting regulatory T cells (T_{reg}) induction, while inhibiting the Th17
84 program²¹. Moreover, RA imparts tissue-homing properties on both CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells by
85 inducing $\alpha 4\beta 7$ and CCR9 expression, guiding their migration to the small intestine (SI)²².
86 However, the role of RA in fostering tissue-residency and the influence of this metabolite on
87 immunity beyond the intestine remain enigmatic.

88

89 Here, we reveal the multifaceted role of RA in regulating tissue immunity. We find that RA is
90 a pivotal factor in directing the tissue-resident transcriptional program in the liver and SI, where
91 RA synergizes with TGF- β to drive T_{RM} cell development. SI T_{RM} cells conditioned by
92 heightened RA signaling persisted independently of TGF- β , implying redundancy between
93 these factors. Furthermore, RA signaling shapes the abundance, phenotype, function and
94 maintenance of T_{RM} cells, with RA signaling blockade facilitating their egress from the SI to
95 draining lymph nodes (LN). Altogether, this work highlights RA as a major coordinator of
96 immunological memory in tissues, offering avenues to enhance local immunity in therapeutic
97 settings.

98 **Results**

99

100 ***CD8⁺ T cells integrate RA signals as a distinct pathway for tissue-residency***

101

102 The transcription factor (TF) T-bet coordinates CD8⁺ T cell differentiation, balancing effector
103 and memory T cell generation²³ and drives T_{RM} cell development across various tissues^{14,17,24}.
104 While skin and liver T_{RM} cells rely on T-bet and downstream IL-15 signals for survival (**Figure**
105 **1A-B and S1A**), SI T_{RM} cells are maintained independently of IL-15²⁵, suggesting a T-bet
106 independent development pathway. Indeed, in experiments using CD8⁺ OT-I transgenic T cells
107 sufficient (wild-type, WT) or deficient for T-bet (*Tbx21*^{-/-}) in combination with recombinant
108 herpes simplex virus (HSV) or lymphocytic choriomeningitis virus (LCMV) expressing OVA
109 infection models, we found that unlike T_{RM} cells in the skin and liver, SI T_{RM} cells flourished
110 in the absence of T-bet (**Figure 1A-C**). This enhanced SI T_{RM} cell generation was not
111 attributable to enhanced tissue entry during the acute phase of infection, nor due to differential
112 expression of the intestinal-homing molecules, $\alpha 4\beta 7$ and CCR9 (**Figure 1D-E**). Rather, T-bet-
113 deficient OT-I cells in SI demonstrated robust persistence over time, while WT cells gradually
114 declined (**Figure 1D**).

115

116 Previous studies have highlighted the importance of CD103 in facilitating SI T_{RM} cell
117 retention^{15,26}. T-bet directly binds to the *Itgae* gene locus²⁴, resulting in elevated CD103
118 expression in *Tbx21*^{-/-} cells (**Figure S1B**). Accordingly, we hypothesized that increased CD103
119 expression might facilitate *Tbx21*^{-/-} cell persistence. To test this, we ablated CD103 (*sgItgae*)
120 in WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells via CRISPR/Cas9 (**Figure S1C-D**). While CD103 deletion in
121 WT cells led to reduced SI T_{RM} cells, *Tbx21*^{-/-} cells were numerically unchanged (**Figure S1E**)
122 indicating that increased *Tbx21*^{-/-} cell lodgment is CD103-independent. While CD103 plays a
123 role in T_{RM} cell retention, it operates with a broader T_{RM} cell differentiation program
124 orchestrated by the cytokine TGF- β ¹⁷. To investigate whether *Tbx21*^{-/-} cells may exhibit
125 increased sensitivity to TGF- β , we co-transferred effector WT with *Tgfb2*^{-/-} or *Tgfb2*^{-/-}*Tbx21*^{-/-}
126 ^{-/-} OT-I cells into recipient mice and isolated SI T_{RM} cells > 30 days (d) later (**Figure 1F**).
127 Remarkably, in the absence of T-bet, SI T_{RM} cells circumvented their reliance on the canonical
128 TGF- β pathway and furthermore, displayed a prototypical SI T_{RM} cell phenotype including
129 CD103 expression, which is typically controlled by TGF- β (**Figure 1G-I**).

130

131 This observation implied that T-bet deficient CD8⁺ T cells utilize alternative tissue cues to
132 engage tissue-residency. To investigate the molecular changes underpinning this distinction,
133 we employed assay of transposase-accessible chromatin sequencing (ATAC-seq) to assess
134 differential chromatin accessibility between WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells isolated from the SI
135 post LCMV-OVA infection. Amongst 6828 differentially accessible chromatin sites identified,
136 cells lacking T-bet exhibited increased accessibility for TF motifs associated with T_{RM} cell
137 differentiation, such as *Bhlhe40*, *Prdm1* and *Fos*^{13,27-29} and for T_{RM} cell-associated genes such
138 as *Itgae* and *Ccr9*^{11,13} (**Figure S1F-G**). In contrast, T-bet deficient cells showed decreased
139 accessibility for TF motifs associated with T_{CIRC} cells such as *Eomes*¹⁴ and for T_{CIRC} cell-
140 associated genes such as *Slpr1* and *Sell*^{11,13} (**Figure S1F-G**). Pathway enrichment analyses
141 revealed that *Tbx21*^{-/-} cells displayed increased accessibility in genes involved in RA signaling
142 compared to WT cells (**Figure S1H**), and exhibited greater accessibility in RA-related motifs,
143 including nuclear receptors RAR and RXR isoforms, as well as reduced motifs for Hic1
144 (**Figure 1J**), an RA-responsive transcriptional repressor recently shown to promote SI T_{RM} cell
145 differentiation^{30,31}. Further, examination of RAR, RXR and Hic1 gene loci revealed the largest
146 change in peak accessibility in *Rara* and *Hic1* genes in *Tbx21*^{-/-} cells (**Figure S1I**), with
147 multiple T-bet binding sites at *Rara* and *Hic1* loci (**Figure S1J**), indicating that T-bet may
148 directly control these TFs. In line with this, we found that upon culture with RA *in vitro*, *Tbx21*^{-/-}
149 cells exhibited enhanced protein expression of RA-dependent molecules such as $\alpha 4\beta 7$, CCR9
150 and Hic1 (**Figure S1K-L**) suggesting that T-bet limits RA responsiveness.

151
152 To investigate whether T_{RM} cell formation could be directly influenced by RA and T-bet
153 interplay, we employed a RAR α/β agonist (AM80; RA ag.) and pan-RA receptor antagonist
154 (AGN194310; RA antag.) to modulate RA signaling *in vivo*. To this end, we transferred
155 effector WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells into mice that were treated with either agent for 6 d or left
156 untreated as a control (Ctrl). As anticipated, WT T_{RM} cells in the SI were numerically increased
157 or decreased upon RA agonism or antagonism, respectively (**Figure 1K-L**). Importantly, the
158 effect of both agents was more pronounced in *Tbx21*^{-/-} cells (**Figure 1K-M and S1M**),
159 suggesting that T-bet modulates RA responsiveness *in vivo*. To explore whether this effect was
160 cell intrinsic, we employed WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells expressing a dominant negative form
161 of RAR α (dnRAR α)³², which abrogates RA signaling (**Figure S1N**). Upon tracking WT and
162 *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells transduced with dnRAR α or control (Ctrl) retroviruses in LCMV-OVA
163 infected mice, we found that dnRAR α expression prevented the enhanced persistence of T-bet

164 deficient SI T_{RM} cells (**Figure 1N-P**). Conversely, the deletion of *Hic1* in *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells
165 did not alter SI T_{RM} cell persistence compared to WT cells (**Figure S1O-Q**), suggesting that
166 the heightened RA sensitivity observed in T-bet deficient cells relies on RAR α rather than
167 *Hic1*. Thus, CD8⁺ T_{RM} cell abundance in the SI is regulated by intersecting transcriptional and
168 cytokine circuits, with T-bet expression controlling the integration of RA signals through
169 RAR α .

170

171 ***RA and TGF- β signaling differentially direct T_{RM} cell development across organs***

172

173 Our results so far indicated that T_{RM} cells could persist in the SI in the absence of T-bet through
174 sustained RA signaling, bypassing their archetypal reliance on TGF- β . Indeed, while T_{RM} cells
175 at barrier sites including the SI and skin are strictly dependent on TGF- β for development^{14,16},
176 those in non-epithelial organs such as the liver exist independently of this cytokine¹⁷ (**Figure**
177 **2A-C**). Hence, we reasoned that T_{RM} cells at distinct tissue locations might also exhibit unique
178 dependencies on extrinsic RA, with RA substituting for TGF- β in sites where the latter is
179 dispensable. To test this, we treated *in vitro* activated OT-I cells with RA prior to transfer into
180 naïve mice treated with the contact sensitizer DNFB to ‘pull’ cells in the skin as described³³
181 and enumerated T_{RM} cells >30 d later. Although RA-treated cells showed impaired infiltration
182 and T_{RM} cell differentiation in the skin, RA enhanced T_{RM} cell development in the SI and liver,
183 with >85% of OT-I cells adopting a T_{RM} cell phenotype in these organs (**Figure 2D-H**). This
184 indicated that skin and liver T_{RM} cells depend on either TGF- β or RA, respectively, whereas SI
185 T_{RM} cells engage both factors for development.

186

187 To explore the role of RA signaling in T_{RM} cell differentiation across organs, we transferred
188 dnRAR α -expressing P14 cells into LCMV-infected mice. During the acute phase of infection
189 (8 d p.i.), disruption of the RA-RAR α axis prevented the formation of short-lived effector cells
190 (KLRG1⁺CD127⁻), leading to increased numbers of memory precursor cells (KLRG1⁻CD127⁺)
191 in lymphoid tissues (**Figure S2A-B**), consistent with previous observations³⁴. Importantly,
192 dnRAR α CD69⁺ T_{RM} cell precursors were reduced in the liver and SI (**Figure S2C-D**),
193 indicating that while detrimental for the generation of circulating memory precursors, RA
194 signaling is essential for T_{RM} cell differentiation. During the memory phase of infection (21 d
195 p.i.), dnRAR α T_{RM} cell numbers were reduced in the liver, kidney and SI, increased in the skin
196 and remained unchanged in other tissues (**Figure 2I-M and Figure S2E-H**). Interestingly, RA

197 signaling was dispensable for T_{RM} cell development in the large intestine (LI) (**Figure 2K and**
198 **S2E-G**). In line with this, dnRAR α cells also showed impaired T_{RM} cell formation in the liver
199 and SI, but not LI in the context of enteric *Listeria monocytogenes* infection, revealing the
200 compartmentalized requirement for RA in the intestine (**Figure S2H-J**). Furthermore, deletion
201 of the RA-induced TF Hic1 in T cells impaired T_{RM} cell formation in the liver and SI but not
202 in the skin (**Figure S2K-M**), suggesting overlapping roles for RAR α and Hic1 in RA signaling
203 in the liver and SI, but distinct roles in the skin.

204

205 To investigate whether RA could compensate for a lack of TGF- β signaling in SI T_{RM} cells, we
206 agonized RA signaling in *Tgfb2*^{-/-} OT-I cells. Remarkably, we found that RA agonism
207 enhanced the number of *Tgfb2*^{-/-} OT-I cells in the SI (**Figure 2N-O and S2N**), resonating with
208 observations made in the context of T-bet deficiency (**Figure 1G-I**). To determine if the
209 recovery of SI T_{RM} cells was solely due to increased migration of effector T cells from
210 enhanced RA signaling, we forced CCR9 expression in WT and *Tgfb2*^{-/-} OT-I cells and
211 assessed SI T_{RM} cell development over time (**Figure 2P**). Although CCR9 overexpression
212 increased T cell entry into the SI (**Figure S2O-P**), it did not rescue the maintenance defect of
213 *Tgfb2*^{-/-} OT-I T_{RM} cells (**Figure 2Q**). Thus, augmenting RA signaling allows SI T_{RM} cells to
214 circumvent their canonical dependence on TGF- β .

215

216 ***RA and TGF- β modulate organ-specific gene signatures associated with T_{RM} cells***

217

218 We have previously shown that TGF- β drives a plethora of gene changes associated with skin
219 T_{RM} cell transcriptional programming¹⁷. However, given this cytokine is dispensable in liver
220 T_{RM} cells that engage a similar tissue-residency gene program, this raises questions as to how
221 parallel tissue-resident features are induced in developmentally diverse T_{RM} cell populations.
222 We therefore asked whether additional microenvironmental factors such as RA might replicate
223 the action of TGF- β in driving T_{RM} cell-associated transcriptional changes. To investigate
224 tissue-residency associated gene alterations induced by RA or TGF- β signaling, we performed
225 RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) on *in vitro* activated CD8⁺ T cells cultured in the presence or
226 absence (Ctrl) of these factors. We then compared these gene expression changes to established
227 transcriptional signatures of T_{RM} cells derived from either the skin, liver or SI versus T_{CIRC}
228 cells¹³ (**Figure 3A**). Here, we found a positive association between the global gene expression
229 in TGF- β -cultured cells, and skin and SI T_{RM} cell organ-specific signatures, but not the liver
230 T_{RM} cell signature. In contrast, RA-cultured cells exhibited gene expression changes associated

231 with SI and liver T_{RM} cells, but not skin T_{RM} cells (**Figure 3B**). Of note, numerous genes
232 modulated by TGF- β that were enriched in skin and SI T_{RM} cells, and genes induced by RA
233 that were enriched in SI and liver T_{RM} cells, were associated with microenvironmental
234 interactions including response to danger or stress (*P2rx7*, *Klrc1*, *Klrk1*) as well as cytokine
235 responsiveness (*Il6ra*, *Il27ra*, *Evi5*) (**Figure S3A**). To determine whether RA-driven
236 transcriptional changes occurred *in vivo*, we profiled the transcriptome of Ctrl and dnRAR α
237 CD69⁺ T_{RM} cells in the liver and SI 14 d after LCMV infection (**Figure 3C**). Consistent with
238 the defect in liver and SI T_{RM} cell differentiation observed in the absence of RA signaling,
239 dnRAR α cells showed gene expression changes associated with a loss of liver and SI T_{RM} cell
240 signatures (**Figure 3D**). This correlation was accompanied with increased expression of T_{CIRC}
241 cell associated genes related to tissue egress (*Ccr7*, *Slpr1*, *Slpr4*) and cell migration (**Figure**
242 **S3B-C**). Additionally, the lack of RA signaling in SI T_{RM} cells caused gene expression changes
243 characteristic of skin T_{RM} cells, including the expression of homing molecules (*Ccr8*, *Ccr10*)
244 (**Figure 3D and S3B**), which aligns with the enhanced T_{RM} cell differentiation of dnRAR α
245 cells in this tissue (**Figure 2I-M**). Together, these results show that while RA or TGF- β induce
246 transcriptional changes associated with either liver or skin T_{RM} cells, respectively, both of these
247 factors instruct the transcriptional signature of T_{RM} cells in the SI.

248

249 ***RA and TGF- β signaling synergize to shape intestine-specific T_{RM} cell identity***

250

251 Our results indicate that both RA and TGF- β contribute to the differentiation of SI T_{RM} cells.
252 Thus, we next asked whether the impact of these factors on T_{RM} cell programming is additive,
253 or if their combined action drives a unique outcome. To explore this, we compared gene
254 expression changes induced by RA, TGF- β or RA+TGF- β in CD8⁺ T cells to the gene signature
255 of T_{RM} cells in the SI (**Figure 3E**). In line with our findings above, showing that increased RA
256 signaling can compensate for the lack of TGF- β (**Figure 2N-O**), we observed substantial
257 overlap among the different culture conditions, suggesting that the combined action of RA and
258 TGF- β drives a similar set of genes within the SI T_{RM} cell gene signature (**Figure 3F**).
259 However, upon evaluating SI-specific genes shared across culture conditions (203 up- and 241
260 downregulated) (**Figure 3F**), the combination of RA and TGF- β resulted in a collective gene
261 expression pattern more closely associated with the SI T_{RM} cell gene signature compared to
262 their individual effects (**Figure 3G**). Moreover, combined RA+TGF- β culture induced a
263 transcriptional program that was more strongly correlated with the SI T_{RM} cell transcriptional

264 profile compared to the effect of either factor in isolation (**Figure 3H**). In addition to these
265 broad transcriptional changes, combining RA and TGF- β resulted in unique outcomes for
266 several SI T_{RM} genes. For instance, we observed synergistic interactions between RA and TGF-
267 β , elevating expression of several genes associated with the SI T_{RM} cell transcriptional program
268 compared to that induced by each factor independently (**Figure S3D**). In addition, we identified
269 a set of 126 genes from the SI T_{RM} cell gene signature that were uniquely regulated when both
270 factors were present (**Table S1**). Together, these findings suggest that RA and TGF- β work
271 synergistically to shape SI T_{RM} cell programming.

272

273 *RA and TGF- β converge to instruct a shared tissue-residency program*

274

275 Although T_{RM} cells exhibit tissue-specific gene signatures, they share a common transcriptional
276 foundation that is required to establish tissue-residency¹¹⁻¹³. Given the varied reliance of T_{RM}
277 cells on either TGF- β or RA signals, we hypothesized that these extrinsic factors share an
278 overlapping ability to drive common gene programs required for tissue-residency. To
279 investigate this, we compared the transcriptomes of CD8⁺ T cells cultured with TGF- β or RA,
280 or both factors combined, to the core transcriptional signature of T_{RM} cells derived from skin,
281 SI and liver versus T_{CIRC} cells¹³ (**Figure 4A**). Strikingly, we identified a significant association
282 between RA-induced gene changes and the core T_{RM} cell signature, an effect that was further
283 amplified when RA was combined with TGF- β (**Figure 4B and S4A**). Notably, RA and TGF-
284 β shared the ability to promote T_{RM} cell differentiation (via induction of *Ahr*, *Cxcr6*, *Rgs1* and
285 others)³⁵⁻³⁷ and to downregulate genes associated with T_{CIRC} cell commitment (e.g. *Ly6c2*, *Sell*,
286 *Tcf7*, *Slamf6*, *Cxcr4*) (**Figure 4C-D**).

287

288 Tissue-residency extends beyond CD8⁺ T cells to encompass innate-like lymphocytes such as
289 liver-residing ILC1 and NKT cells, with which they share a common transcriptional program¹³.
290 Accordingly, we found that tissue-residency genes induced in CD8⁺ T cells by RA and/or TGF-
291 β mirrored gene expression in liver ILC1 and NKT cells. In particular, both tissue-factors
292 promoted the expression of genes universally upregulated by CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells, liver ILC1, and
293 NKT (e.g., *Cxcr6*, *Osgin1*, *Gpr34*, *Gpr55*, *Cish*) while repressing genes associated with a
294 circulating fate (e.g. *Cxcr4*, *Sell*, *Tcf7*) (**Figure 4E**). Together, these results underscore the
295 central role of RA in shaping tissue-resident transcriptional signatures across distinct immune
296 cell lineages. Despite the shared ability of both factors to regulate genes of the core T_{RM} cell

297 program, the action of RA was magnified in the presence of TGF- β , revealing their
298 combinatorial footprint in driving the core tissue-residency program.

299

300 ***RA and TGF- β conditioning drives phenotypic changes associated with SI T_{RM} cells***

301

302 Given that RA and TGF- β synergize to shape both core and SI T_{RM}-specific cell differentiation
303 programs, we next asked whether the combination of these factors could recapitulate the
304 phenotypic maturation of CD8⁺ T cells into T_{RM}-like cells *in vitro*. Using CD69 and CD103 as
305 surrogate markers for SI T_{RM} cell programming, we found that RA and TGF- β individually
306 drove the expression of either CD69 or CD103 on CD8⁺ T cells, respectively (**Figure 4F-G**).
307 Intriguingly, co-expression of CD69 and CD103 on the majority of cultured CD8⁺ T cells was
308 observed only when both factors were present (**Figure 4F-G**), which was also true for cultured
309 human CD8⁺ T cells (**Figure 4H-I**). To further investigate the extent to which RA and TGF- β
310 conditioned CD8⁺ T cells resembled *bona fide* SI T_{RM} populations, we used high-dimensional
311 spectral cytometry to compare their protein expression profiles, focusing on markers
312 characteristic of T_{RM} cells (residency-associated) or T_{CIRC} cells (circulation-associated)
313 (**Figure S4C**). Akin to *bona fide* T_{RM} cells, RA and TGF- β -conditioned cells suppressed
314 “circulation-associated” molecules (e.g. CD62L, Ly6C, NKG2D) and induced “residency-
315 associated” markers (e.g. CD38, CD39, CD73, β 7-integrin) *in vitro* (**Figure S4C-D**).
316 Remarkably, while *in vitro* cultured CD8⁺ T cells shared a close resemblance to splenic T_{CIRC}
317 cells, pre-conditioning these cells with RA and TGF- β led them to adopt a SI T_{RM} cell-like
318 phenotype (**Figure S4E**). Collectively, these results underscore the ability of RA and TGF- β
319 to imprint the CD8⁺ T_{RM} cell associated phenotype.

320

321 ***RA signaling regulates the long-term maintenance of conventional intestinal lymphocytes***

322

323 Our results so far uncovered RA as an alternative driver of tissue-residency. Modulating RA
324 signals during the effector phase (**Figure 1K-M and Figure S5A-F**) and disrupting the RA-
325 RAR α axis (**Figure S2A-D**) had a substantial impact on SI T_{RM} cell differentiation. However,
326 since RA signaling controls SI homing molecules like CCR9, defective tissue entry might
327 primarily hinder SI T_{RM} cell generation during RA signaling deficiency. To test this, we forced
328 CCR9 expression in Ctrl and dnRAR α P14 cells and evaluated SI T_{RM} development (**Figure**
329 **5A**). Although CCR9 overexpression enhanced T cell entry into the SI, dnRAR α T_{RM} cells

330 were still lost during the memory phase (**Figure 5B-C**), indicating that RA signaling deficiency
331 affects SI T_{RM} cells beyond tissue homing. To determine if sustained RA signaling was
332 necessary for the maintenance of established T_{RM} populations, we infected mice containing
333 naïve P14 cells with LCMV and blocked RA signals for 7 d during the memory phase (>70 d
334 p.i.). Strikingly, inhibiting RA signaling after memory establishment resulted in a significant
335 decline of P14 SI T_{RM} cells, leaving splenic T_{CIRC} unaltered (**Figure 5D-F**). Although blocking
336 RA signaling had a more dramatic impact on CD69⁺CD103⁻ T_{RM} cells compared to their
337 CD69⁺CD103⁺ counterparts, an overall decline in total CD69⁺ T_{RM} cells was observed
338 irrespective of CD103 expression (**Figure 5F**). Additionally, immunofluorescence microscopy
339 showed a reduced presence of P14 cells within the SI villi following RA antagonism (**Figure**
340 **5G**). Collectively, these results underscore the pivotal role of RA signaling in sustaining the SI
341 T_{RM} cell compartment.

342

343 We next sought to investigate the impact of RA antagonism on the maintenance of other
344 immune cell populations resident in the intestine, including conventional TCRαβ CD4⁺ and
345 CD8αβ⁺ T cells and unconventional TCRαβ CD8αα⁺ and TCRγδ T cells, which are linked to
346 tissue repair and homeostatic functions³⁸. We found that inhibiting RA signaling caused a
347 marked reduction in conventional TCRαβ CD4⁺ and CD8αβ⁺ T cells expressing tissue-
348 residency markers (**Figure 5H-K and 5M**). In contrast, unconventional TCRαβ CD8αα⁺ and
349 TCRγδ T cells numbers remained unaltered, resulting in a higher proportion of these cells in
350 the SI of treated mice (**Figure 5K-L**). Thus, RA signaling is essential for maintaining CD4⁺
351 and CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells, whereas TCRαβ CD8αα⁺ and TCRγδ cells appear to persist in the SI
352 independently of RA signaling.

353

354 To understand the mechanism by which RA signaling promotes SI T_{RM} cell maintenance, we
355 conducted RNA-seq analysis on SI T_{RM} cells following RA antagonist treatment (**Figure S6A**).
356 We observed no significant changes in apoptosis-related molecules, such as Bcl2 and Bim, at
357 both gene and protein level (**Figure S6A-C**). Additionally, we found that the receptor P2RX7,
358 which promotes SI T_{RM} cell survival and metabolic fitness³⁹, was downregulated upon RA
359 signaling blockade (**Figure S6D**), consistent with a role for RA in P2RX7 expression⁴⁰.
360 However, P2RX7-ablated SI T_{RM} cells still decayed following RA antagonism (**Figure S6E-**
361 **G**). Thus, SI T_{RM} cell loss did not appear to be linked to increased cell death *in situ*. Recent
362 work highlights retrograde migration as a key mechanism by which T_{RM} cells decay in
363 peripheral tissues^{41,42}. Supporting this, RA antagonism resulted in increased expression of

364 tissue egress genes (*Klf2*, *Slpr5*, *Zeb2*)⁴³ in SI T_{RM} cells (**Figure S6B**). To test if T_{RM} cells
365 leave the SI upon RA signaling blockade, we used a fate-mapping system based on the
366 transcription factor Hobit that is specifically expressed by T_{RM} cells (*Hobit*^{cre-tdTomato};*Rosa26*<sup>LsL-
367 YFP</sup>) (**Figure 6A and S6H**), and was previously used to track T_{RM} cells and their progeny after
368 antigen recall⁴⁴. Using this system, we observed a decrease in SI T_{RM} cells and increase in SI
369 ‘ex-T_{RM}’ cells, along with a rise in T_{RM} and ‘ex-T_{RM}’ cells in mesenteric lymph nodes (mLN)
370 following RA signaling blockade, suggesting active migration away from the SI (**Figure 6B-
371 C**). Furthermore, treatment with FTY720, which inhibits the S1P-signaling pathway and
372 impedes tissue egress, alongside RA blockade, prevented the decrease in SI T_{RM} cells and the
373 increase in mLN T cells (**Figure 6D-E and S6I-J**). Supporting this, P14 cells were less
374 frequently found within the SI epithelium, with some closely associated with lymphatics
375 following RA signaling blockade (**Figure 6F and Video S1**). Collectively, these results
376 indicate that sustained RA signaling promotes the long-term maintenance of SI T_{RM} cells by
377 limiting their migration to draining LNs via the S1P pathway.

378

379 *RA replicates features of T_{RM} cells driven by microbial diversification*

380

381 Tissue immune homeostasis requires an optimal balance of tissue-resident lymphocyte
382 abundance and function. It is well established that TGF- β can modulate the phenotype and
383 function of T_{RM} cells^{17,37}, raising the question whether RA could exert similar effects.
384 Following the temporal antagonism of RA signaling in naïve mice, we found that endogenous
385 CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells isolated from the SI or liver exhibited reduced expression of the purinergic
386 receptor P2RX7 and upregulation of memory-associated markers TCF-1 and CD127 (**Figure
387 7A-B**). Conversely, RA agonism enhanced P2RX7 expression and reduced TCF-1 and CD127
388 expression on these T_{RM} populations (**Figure 7C-D**), suggesting a multifaceted role of RA
389 signaling in modulating both T_{RM} cell abundance and phenotype. Although RA is mainly
390 produced by the host, the microbiota significantly contributes to RA production, either by
391 metabolizing vitamin A and its derivatives, or by directly producing RA⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷. Thus, we reasoned
392 that T_{RM} cells found in mice with increased microbial experience may exhibit phenotypic
393 features similar to those observed following RA agonism. To test this, we employed ‘dirty’
394 mice that carry a diverse microbiome and an immune activation state more similar to adult
395 humans⁴⁸⁻⁵². We cohoused dirty mice with specific-pathogen free (SPF) mice for 30 d, allowing
396 their microbiome to equilibrate (**Figure 7E and S7A-B**). This process allowed the introduction
397 of various bacteria taxa in SPF mice, including *Lactobacillus spp.*, which are known to produce

398 RA⁴⁵ (**Figure S7B-C**). Consistent with this, microbial exposure increased RA levels in
399 cohoused mice related to their SPF counterparts (**Figure 7F**). Notably, we did not observe an
400 expansion of activated or memory CD8⁺ T cells in the blood and spleen (**Figure S7D-E**),
401 suggesting that systemic pathogen insults were limited in cohoused mice. Instead, we observed
402 a pronounced shift of the SI immune landscape from unconventional to adaptive lymphocyte
403 populations in microbially diverse mice, with an increased abundance of conventional TCRαβ
404 CD4⁺ and CD8αβ⁺ T cells expressing tissue-residency markers, as well as the presence of
405 CD4⁺CD8αα⁺ regulatory T cells (**Figure 7G-J and S7E**), a population dependent on RA
406 signaling for development⁵³. In contrast, we noticed a concomitant decrease in the frequency
407 of unconventional TCRαβ CD8αα⁺ and TCRγδ T cells (**Figure 7G-J and S7E**), the reverse of
408 changes occurring after RA signaling blockade (**Figure 6D-G**). Compared to SPF mice,
409 conventional TCRαβ CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells in both liver and SI of microbially diverse mice exhibited
410 phenotypic changes which paralleled those observed after RA signaling agonism (**Figure 7D**
411 **and 7K-N**), implying that the augmented CD8⁺ T_{RM} cell compartment and the altered
412 phenotype of those cells upon microbial conditioning may be driven in part by increased RA
413 signaling.

414

415 In addition to promoting CD8⁺ T_{RM} cell development, we also noted that modulating RA
416 signaling could impact T cell function, whereby disruption of RA signaling in dnRARα SI T_{RM}
417 cells resulted in heightened production of proinflammatory cytokines IFNγ and TNF 21 d p.i
418 (**Figure S7F-H**). Conversely, RA-agonized OT-I cells showed a reduced capacity to produce
419 IFNγ and TNFα in the SI >30d after transfer (**Figure 7O and S7I-K**). A similar decrease in
420 CD8⁺ T_{RM} cell functionality was evident after cohousing SPF mice with dirty mice for 30 d
421 (**Figure 7P**), indicating that RA signaling and increased microbial exposure fine-tune the
422 balance between the quantity and quality of CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells, potentially minimizing tissue-
423 damage at barrier sites exposed to external stimuli. Collectively, our data reveal the importance
424 of RA signals in regulating the landscape of tissue-resident lymphocytes, acting as a bridge
425 through which local immunity can be shaped in response to microbial diversity.

426 **Discussion**

427

428 Tissue homeostasis relies on the strategic positioning of immune cells including T_{RM} cells
429 within tissues. Despite phenotypic diversity between organs, T_{RM} cells develop through a
430 common transcriptional framework that enforces tissue-residency. Paradoxically, this program
431 operates in drastically different microenvironments, raising the question of how T cells
432 integrate distinct cues to adopt a common T_{RM} cell fate. While host-derived molecules
433 including TGF- β are essential for tissue-resident lymphocyte programming in some organs,
434 analogous factors remain poorly defined. Moreover, whether such tissue-derived cues can
435 cooperate with microenvironmental factors to drive tissue-residency was previously unknown.
436 Here, we reveal that RA shaped numerous aspects of tissue-resident lymphocyte biology, in
437 part by collaborating with TGF- β . Beyond its role in T cell migration, we found that RA
438 signaling altered T_{RM} cell phenotype, function and durability. Lastly, enhancing RA signaling
439 could mirror the tissue-resident lymphocyte landscape in mice with diversified microbiota,
440 reflecting the complex interplay between local factors and environmental cues in regulating
441 tissue immunity.

442

443 T_{RM} cell programming is orchestrated by transcriptional regulators and microenvironmental
444 cues, which induce the retention and survival of T_{RM} precursor cells while suppressing T_{CIRC}
445 cell differentiation¹¹⁻¹³. While this process results in a shared T_{RM} cell core signature across
446 tissues, T_{RM} cells residing in individual tissues develop unique signatures that differentiate
447 them from T_{CIRC} cells. Until now, the microenvironmental factors influencing these tissue-
448 specific programs have remained elusive. Here we show that T_{RM} cells exhibit distinct
449 dependencies for TGF- β and RA signals, whereby skin and liver T_{RM} cells rely on either TGF-
450 β or RA, respectively, and SI T_{RM} cells require both factors for development. Mechanistically,
451 TGF- β and RA both induce genes essential for T_{RM} cell development and/or migration,
452 including *Ahr*, *Cxcr6* and *Rgs1*³⁵⁻³⁷, indicating that either factor is sufficient to drive core tissue-
453 residency programming. Nonetheless, TGF- β and RA also induced distinct gene sets unique to
454 skin or liver T_{RM} cells, respectively, while their combined action shaped SI T_{RM} cell identity.
455 The divergent roles of TGF- β and RA may be attributable to their differing presence across
456 tissues. Active TGF- β is abundant within epithelial microenvironments⁵⁴, while RA
457 bioavailability varies. RA precursors, such as retinol, are absorbed in the SI, stored in the liver,
458 and redistributed to various body sites before local conversion into RA by epithelial, stromal
459 and dendritic cell (DC) populations^{46,55,56}. Although RA is abundant in the SI and liver^{46,55,56},

460 its availability in specific skin niches is unclear. Further work will determine whether skin T_{RM}
461 cells exhibit an intrinsic defect in RA signaling pathways or lack access to RA signaling *in situ*.

462

463 While RA signaling is crucial for inducing gut-homing molecules during T cell priming in SI
464 draining lymph nodes (LN)^{22,57}, it also licenses SI T_{RM} cell differentiation prior to tissue
465 entry⁵⁸. Resonating with this, migratory DCs precondition naïve T cells for T_{RM} cell
466 differentiation by presenting active TGF- β in skin draining LNs⁵⁹. Since DCs produce TGF- β
467 and RA^{56,57}, these molecules could synergize during T cell priming, with this effect being
468 potentially amplified when T_{RM} precursors cells undergo maturation in the SI. Interestingly,
469 the combined actions of TGF- β and RA extend beyond CD8⁺ T cells, shaping the
470 differentiation of multiple lymphocyte populations in the SI^{21,53,60,61}. In particular, the
471 combination of TGF- β and RA is essential for establishing oral tolerance by favoring peripheral
472 Treg cell development over Th17 cells²¹. While this synergy seems primarily confined to the
473 SI, TGF- β or RA may interface with additional local factors to drive tissue-specific T_{RM}
474 differentiation in other locations.

475

476 T_{RM} cells confer prolonged immune protection by persisting in peripheral tissues. At epithelial
477 sites, continuous microenvironmental signals, such as TGF- β , are crucial for T_{RM} cell
478 longevity^{31,62}. Mechanistically, purinergic signaling through P2RX7 or CD38 enhances TGF-
479 β sensitivity in T_{RM} cells, thereby supporting their maintenance^{39,63}. Unlike TGF- β , sustained
480 RA signaling is essential for retaining SI T_{RM} cells locally by limiting their retrograde
481 migration. Although this migration pattern was observed early during T_{RM} cell differentiation
482 (<20 d p.i.)^{41,42} or in mature T_{RM} cells following antigen recall⁴⁴, our study demonstrates that
483 this process can also occur long after the antigen clearance (>70 days p.i.). Furthermore,
484 retrograde migration induced by interrupted RA signaling predominantly affects the CD103⁻
485 T_{RM} cell population, which can robustly expand during secondary infections^{64,65}. As RA levels
486 can fluctuate during infections⁶⁶⁻⁶⁸, these fluctuations may prompt SI T_{RM} cells to retreat to
487 draining LNs and mount effective mucosal responses.

488

489 Vitamin A-deficiency is a prevalent cause of nutrient deficiency linked with impaired adaptive
490 immunity^{69,70}, in line with our data highlighting that RA is required for the abundance and
491 maintenance of CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells in specific organs. Considering the significant correlation
492 between T_{RM} cell density and immune defense^{26,71,72}, the loss of T_{RM} cells during vitamin-A
493 deficiency likely to compromise immune protection. In addition to dietary effects, altered

494 microbial diversity reshapes the adaptive immune compartment^{48,50,51}, while unconventional T
495 cells remain numerically stable, as seen in germ-free mice^{73,74}. Interestingly, we found that
496 both RA and microbial diversity diminished pro-inflammatory cytokine production in T_{RM}
497 cells, consistent with observations that microbially enriched mice exhibit compromised
498 adaptive immune responses after influenza infection⁵¹. While this loss of protection could be
499 tissue and context-specific, it highlights the balance between increased T_{RM} cell numbers and
500 restricted cytokine production to prevent excessive immune activation, potentially
501 compromising pathogen control.

502

503 Together, our work highlights RA as a key orchestrator of immunological memory,
504 coordinating multiple aspects of T cell biology within peripheral organs, from tissue-residency
505 programming to effector function. Harnessing the potential of RA through cell conditioning or
506 microbiota manipulation may enhance the generation of protective T_{RM} cells or eliminate
507 autoimmune tissue-resident populations, optimizing local immunity and improving disease
508 outcomes.

509

510 **Limitations of the study**

511 Our study primarily employed TCR transgenic CD8⁺ T cells in the context of LCMV infection,
512 which generate a T_{RM1}-biased population that do not fully capture the diversity of CD8⁺ T cell
513 responses⁷⁵. As such, the contribution of RA signaling to non-canonical endogenous responses
514 such as T_{RM17} was not investigated. Additionally, we used an antagonist to study the impact
515 of RA signaling on T_{RM} cell maintenance, and thus it remains unclear whether the observed
516 effects are intrinsic to T_{RM} cells or mediated indirectly through other cell types. Although we
517 showed that RA blockade prompts the retrograde migration of SI T_{RM} cells, a fraction of these
518 cells may undergo apoptosis in the lamina propria before reaching draining LNs. Finally, while
519 RA-producing taxa like *Lactobacillus* were more abundant in cohoused mice, other
520 unidentified bacteria likely produce RA additional microbial species and metabolites could
521 contribute to the observed changes in T_{RM} cells beyond RA signaling.

522

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535

536 **Author contributions**

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544

545 **Declaration of interests**

546 The authors declare no competing interests.

547

548 **Figure legends**

549

550 **Figure 1. CD8⁺ T cells integrate RA signals as an alternative pathway for T_{RM} cell**
551 **differentiation. (A-E)** WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells were co-transferred into recipient mice and
552 primed with **(A)** HSV-OVA or **(B-E)** LCMV-OVA. **(A-C)** OT-I cells were isolated >30 d p.i.
553 from indicated tissues. *(Top)* numbers of CD69⁺ OT-I cells from indicated tissues and *(bottom)*
554 ratio of *Tbx21*^{-/-} and WT OT-I cells. **(D)** Enumeration of CD69⁺ OT-I SI cells and **(E)** frequency
555 of α4β7 and CCR9-expressing OT-I cells isolated from the mLN at indicated times p.i. **(F-I)**
556 Effector WT and *Tgfb2*^{-/-} or *Tgfb2*^{-/-}*Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells were co-transferred into recipient mice
557 and isolated from the SI >30 d later, as depicted in **(F)**. **(G)** Enumeration and **(H)** ratio of
558 CD69⁺ OT-I cells **(I)** Frequency of CD69⁺CD103⁺ OT-I cells. **(J)** WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells
559 were primed with LCMV-OVA. CD69⁺ OT-I cells were sort-purified from the SI 8 d p.i. and
560 subjected to ATAC-seq. Shown is the motif deviation derived from genes with DACR between
561 WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells. **(K-M)** Effector WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells were co-transferred
562 into naïve recipients. Mice were treated every other day with DMSO (Ctrl), AM80 (RA ag.) or
563 AGN194310 (RA antag.) from 0 to 6 d post-transfer and OT-I cells were isolated from the SI
564 30 d post-transfer. **(K-L)** Enumeration and **(M)** ratios of WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells from RA
565 ag. or RA antag.-treated mice compared to Ctrl-treated mice. **(N-P)** WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells
566 were transduced with either empty (Ctrl-RV) or dnRARα (dnRARα-RV) retroviruses.
567 Transduced OT-I cells were co-transferred into LCMV-OVA infected recipient mice and
568 isolated from the SI 21 d p.i., as depicted in **(N)**. **(O)** Enumeration and **(P)** ratios of WT and
569 *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells transduced with either Ctrl or dnRARα retroviruses. Data are pooled from
570 2-3 independent experiments (A, B, D, G-I, K-P) or representative of 1-3 independent
571 experiments (C, E, J-L) with n = 8-17 (A, B, D) or n = 3-8 (C, E, G-I, K-P) mice per group.
572 *p≤0.05, **p≤0.01, ****p≤0.0001, n.s. = non significant, Wilcoxon test (A, B, E), paired t-
573 test (C, D, G), unpaired t-test (H, I, K-P). Bars represent the mean; symbols represent individual
574 mice.

575

576 **Figure 2. RA and TGF-β signals choreograph T_{RM} cell tropism across organs. (A-C)**
577 Effector WT and *Tgfb2*^{-/-} OT-I cells were transferred at 1:1 ratio into recipient mice and
578 isolated from indicated tissues 30 d later, as depicted in **(A)**. **(B)** Enumeration and **(C)** ratio of
579 *Tgfb2*^{-/-} and WT OT-I cells for indicated populations. **(D-H)** Effector OT-I cells were cultured
580 in the absence (-RA) or presence (+RA) of RA, transferred into DNFB-treated mice and

581 isolated from indicated tissues 30 d later, as depicted in (D). (E) Enumeration and (F) ratio of
582 \pm RA-cultured OT-I cells in indicated tissues. (G) Representative flow cytometry plots
583 depicting expression of the indicated markers in \pm RA-cultured OT-I cells from indicated
584 tissues, and (H) frequency of CD69⁺CD103⁺ (*skin, SI*) CD69⁺CD38⁺ (*liver*) OT-I cells isolated
585 from indicated tissues and culture conditions. (I-M) P14 cells were transduced with either
586 empty (Ctrl-RV) or dnRAR α (dnRAR α -RV) retroviruses, co-transferred into LCMV infected,
587 DNFB-treated recipient mice and isolated from indicated tissues 21 d p.i., as depicted in (I).
588 (J) Enumeration and (K) ratio of Ctrl or dnRAR α P14 cells in indicated tissues. (L)
589 Representative flow cytometry plots depicting expression of indicated markers in Ctrl or
590 dnRAR α P14 cells from indicated tissues, and (M) frequency of CD69⁺CD103⁺ (*skin, SI*)
591 CD69⁺CD38⁺ (*liver*) Ctrl or dnRAR α P14 cells isolated from indicated tissues. (N-P) Effector
592 WT and *Tgfb2*^{-/-} OT-I cells were co-transferred into naïve recipients. Mice were treated with
593 DMSO (Ctrl) or AM80 (RA ag.) from 0 to 6 d post-transfer and OT-I cells isolated from the
594 SI 30 d post-transfer, as depicted in (N). (O) Numbers of CD69⁺ OT-I cells for indicated
595 genotypes and treatments. (P-Q) Effector WT and *Tgfb2*^{-/-} OT-I cells were transduced with
596 either empty (Ctrl-RV) or CCR9 (CCR9-RV) retroviruses, co-transferred into naïve recipient
597 mice and isolated from the SI 30 d p.i., as depicted in (P). (Q) Numbers of transduced CD69⁺
598 WT and *Tgfb2*^{-/-} OT-I cells isolated 30 d p.i. from the SI. Data are pooled from 2-3 independent
599 experiments (A-F, J-Q) or representative of 2 independent experiments (H) with n = 7-10 or n
600 = 4-5 (H) mice per group, *p \leq 0.05 **p \leq 0.01, ***p \leq 0.001, ****p \leq 0.0001, n.s. = non
601 significant, paired t-test (B, E, J, Q), unpaired t-test (H, M), ordinary one-way ANOVA with
602 Tukey's multiple comparisons test (K), or ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparisons test
603 (C, F, O). Bars represent the mean; symbols represent individual mice.

604

605 **Figure 3. RA and TGF- β signals differentially program tissue-residency across organs.**

606 (A-F) Effector CD8⁺ T cells were cultured in the absence (Ctrl) or presence of TGF- β , RA or
607 RA+TGF- β for 7 d, and subjected to RNA-seq. (A-B) Gene expression data from TGF- β or
608 RA-cultured CD8⁺ T cells was compared to skin, liver and SI T_{RM} cells transcriptional
609 signatures from GSE70813¹³, as depicted in (A). (B) Scatter plots showing transcriptional
610 changes for skin, liver and SI T_{RM} cells vs splenic T_{CIRC} cells (*y-axis*) against CD8⁺ T cells
611 cultured with (*top*) TGF- β or (*bottom*) RA versus Ctrl (*x-axis*). Dots represent the top 200 up-
612 (*orange*) or downregulated (*purple*) genes in T_{RM} cells from indicated tissues versus T_{CIRC}
613 cells. Black line represents least-squares regression line fitted to all points. (C-D) P14 cells

614 were transduced with either empty (Ctrl-RV) or dnRAR α (dnRAR α -RV) retroviruses, and co-
615 transferred into LCMV infected recipient mice. CD69⁺ transduced P14 cells were sorted from
616 indicated tissues 14 d p.i., and subjected to bulk RNA-seq. Gene expression data from Ctrl or
617 dnRAR α CD69⁺ P14 cells from indicated tissues was compared to skin, liver and SI T_{RM} cells
618 transcriptional signatures from GSE70813¹³, as depicted in (C). (D) Scatter plots showing
619 transcriptional changes for skin, liver and SI T_{RM} cells vs splenic T_{CIRC} cells (*y-axis*) against
620 Ctrl vs dnRAR α CD69⁺ P14 cells (*x-axis*) from indicated tissues. Dots represent the top 200
621 up- (*orange*) or downregulated (*purple*) genes in T_{RM} cells from indicated tissues versus T_{CIRC}
622 cells. Black line represents least-squares regression line fitted to all points. (E-H) SI T_{RM} cell
623 transcriptional signature (GSE70813¹³) was compared to gene expression data from TGF- β ,
624 RA or RA+TGF- β -cultured CD8⁺ T cells, as depicted in (E). (F) UpSet plots showing SI T_{RM}
625 cell signature genes and their DE status within CD8⁺ T cells cultured with TGF- β , RA or
626 RA+TGF- β . (G) Heatmap showing expression of SI T_{RM} signature genes co-regulated by TGF-
627 β , RA and RA+TGF- β , as compared to Ctrl (203 up- and 241 downregulated), as depicted in
628 (F). (H) Bubble plot of log-odds ratios (LORs) and p-values obtained from comparing
629 transcriptional changes in SI T_{RM} cells vs T_{CIRC} cells to those in TGF- β , RA or RA+TGF- β -
630 cultured CD8⁺ T cells. Data are representative of 2 independent experiments with n = 2-3
631 samples (A-B, E-H) or n = 4 samples (C-D) per group.

632

633 **Figure 4. RA and TGF- β signals drive the shared tissue-residency program. (A-E)** Gene
634 expression data from TGF- β , RA or RA+TGF- β -cultured CD8⁺ T cells was compared to the
635 core residency gene signature shared by skin, liver and SI T_{RM} cells from GSE70813¹³, as
636 depicted in (A). (B) Scatter plots showing gene expression changes for CD8⁺ T cells cultured
637 with TGF- β , RA or RA+TGF- β versus Ctrl (*y-axis*) against T_{RM} cells vs T_{CIRC} cells (*x-axis*) for
638 core T_{RM} cell signature genes. Black line represents least-squares regression line fitted to all
639 points. (C) UpSet plots showing core T_{RM} signature genes derived from GSE70813¹³ shared
640 with CD8⁺ T cells cultured with TGF- β , RA or RA+TGF- β . Up- and downregulated genes are
641 depicted in orange and purple, respectively. (D) Venn diagrams showing core T_{RM} signature
642 genes shared with CD8⁺ T cells cultured with TGF- β , RA or RA+TGF- β . Up- and
643 downregulated genes are depicted in orange and purple, respectively. (E) Heatmap showing
644 expression of DEGs co-regulated by TGF- β , RA and RA+TGF- β from (D) in indicated
645 populations. (F-I) Murine (F-G) and human (H-I) effector CD8⁺ T cells were cultured in the
646 absence (Ctrl) or presence of TGF- β , RA or RA+TGF- β for 7 d (mouse) or 21 d (human). (F,
647 H) Representative flow cytometry plots and (G, I) quantification of CD69 and CD103

648 expression in CD8⁺ T cells for indicated conditions. Data are representative of 2 independent
649 experiments with n = 2-3 samples or n = 1 donor (H-I) per group.

650

651 **Figure 5. RA signals sustain adaptive cellular immunity in the intestine.** (A-C) P14 cells
652 were co-transduced with either control Ametrine (Ctrl-Amt) or dnRAR α -GFP (dnRAR α -GFP)
653 retroviruses, as well as control-GFP (Ctrl-GFP) or CCR9 Ametrine (CCR9-Amt) retroviruses
654 and were transferred into LCMV infected recipient mice and isolated from indicated tissues 7
655 and 21 d p.i., as depicted in (A). (B) Numbers of transduced (*left*) P14 cells at 7 d p.i. and
656 (*right*) CD69⁺ P14 cells at 21 d p.i. isolated from the SI and (C) Ratio of transduced Ctrl and
657 dnRAR α P14 cells in indicated tissues at 21 d p.i. (D-M) Mice received P14 cells and were
658 infected with LCMV. At >30 d p.i., mice were treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or AGN194310 (RA
659 antag.) for 6 d and were isolated from indicated tissues the following day as depicted in (D).
660 (E-F) Enumeration of (E) splenic and (F) SI P14 cell populations in Ctrl or RA antag. treated
661 mice. (G) Confocal microscopy images of SI showing collagen IV (*magenta*), P14 cells
662 (Thy1.1, *green*) and epithelium (EpCAM, *blue*) in Ctrl and RA antag. treated mice. A zoomed-
663 in view of P14 cells is shown (*yellow inset*). (H-K) UMAP analysis of SI intra-epithelial
664 lymphocytes (SI-IEL). Cells were color-coded according to (H) lymphocyte lineages or (I)
665 treatment. (J) Frequency and (K) volcano plot of lymphocyte subset abundance between Ctrl
666 and treated groups. (L-M) Enumeration of (L) TCR $\gamma\delta$ ⁺ and CD8 $\alpha\alpha$ ⁺ and (M) CD8⁺CD69⁺ and
667 CD4⁺ CD69⁺ T cells from the SI >30 d p.i. Data are pooled from 2-3 independent experiments
668 with n = 5-15 mice per group. *p \leq 0.05, **p \leq 0.01, ***p \leq 0.001, ****p \leq 0.0001, n.s. = non
669 significant, Wilcoxon test (B), Two-way ANOVA (C) or unpaired t-test (D-M). Bars represent
670 the mean; symbols represent individual mice.

671

672 **Figure 6. RA signals limit the retrograde migration of SI T_{RM} cells.** (A-C) Mice received
673 P14 *Hobit*^{cre-tdTom}:*Rosa26*^{LsL-YFP} T cells and were infected with LCMV. At >30 d p.i., mice were
674 treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or AGN194310 (RA antag.) for 6 d and isolated from indicated
675 tissues the following day, as depicted in (A). (B-C) Enumeration of (B) P14 YFP⁺TdTom⁺ T_{RM}
676 cells and (C) P14 YFP⁺TdTom⁺ T_{RM} cells and P14 YFP⁺TdTom⁻ ‘ex-T_{RM}’ cells isolated from
677 indicated organs of Ctrl or RA antag. treated mice. (D-E) Mice received P14 cells and were
678 infected with LCMV. At >30 d p.i., mice were treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or AGN194310 (RA
679 antag.) for 6 d, while receiving FTY720 or Cyclodextran (Ctrl) daily before P14 cells were
680 isolated from indicated organs at 7 d post treatment, as depicted in (D). (E) Enumeration of SI

681 and mLN P14 cell populations for indicated conditions. **(F)** Mice received Thy1.1⁺ P14 cells
682 and were infected with LCMV. At >30 d p.i., mice were treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or
683 AGN194310 (RA antag.) for 6 d, and were sacrificed the following day. Confocal microscopy
684 images of SI showing lymphatic endothelium (LyVE-1, *red*), P14 cells (Thy1.1, *green*) and
685 epithelium (EpCAM, *blue*) in Ctrl and RA antag. treated mice. A zoomed-in view of P14 cells
686 is shown (*yellow inset*). A zoomed-in 3D-rendered view of P14 cells in relation to lymphatics
687 and epithelium is shown (*yellow*). P14 cells in contact with lymphatics are depicted with
688 arrowheads (*white*). Data are pooled from 2-3 independent experiments with n = 8-16 mice per
689 group. **p≤0.01, ***p≤0.001, ****p≤0.0001, n.s. = non significant, unpaired t-test. Bars
690 represent the mean; symbols represent individual mice.

691

692 **Figure 7. RA imprinting typifies the T_{RM} cell landscape after microbial conditioning. (A-**
693 **B)** Naïve C57BL/6 mice were treated every other day with DMSO (Ctrl) or AGN194310 (RA
694 antag.) for 7 days and endogenous CD8⁺ T cells were isolated from the SI and liver, as depicted
695 in **(A)**. **(B)** Heatmap showing expression of P2RX7, TCF1 and CD127 in indicated populations
696 and organs. **(C-D)** Naïve C57BL/6 mice were treated every other day with DMSO (Ctrl) or
697 AM80 (RA ag.) for 7 days and endogenous CD8⁺ T cells were isolated from the SI and liver,
698 as depicted in **(C)**. **(D)** Heatmap showing expression of P2RX7, TCF1 and CD127 in indicated
699 populations and organs. **(E-F)** Mice were housed in SPF conditions or cohoused with ‘dirty’
700 mice for >30 d, as depicted in **(E)**. **(F)** Serum RA concentrations of SPF, cohoused mice, or
701 mice receiving all-trans retinoic acid (atRA) prior to sample collection determined by ELISA
702 analysis. **(G-J)** UMAP analysis of SI-IEL. Cells were color-coded according to **(G)**
703 lymphocyte lineages or **(H)** treatment. **(I)** Frequency and **(J)** volcano plot of lymphocyte subset
704 abundance between Ctrl and cohoused groups. **(K)** Enumeration of endogenous CD8αβ CD69⁺
705 SI T_{RM} cells isolated from SPF or cohoused mice and **(L)** expression of indicated molecules
706 depicted as a heatmap. **(M)** Enumeration of endogenous CD8αβ CD69⁺ liver T_{RM} cells isolated
707 from SPF or cohoused mice and **(N)** expression of indicated molecules depicted as a heatmap.
708 **(O)** Mice received effector OT-I cells, were treated every other day with DMSO or AM80 (RA
709 ag.) from 0 to 6 d post-transfer and rested for >30 d. **(P)** SPF mice received OT-I cells and
710 were infected with Lm-OVA. At 30 d p.i., mice were kept in SPF conditions or cohoused with
711 ‘dirty’ mice for >30 d. OT-I T cells were isolated from the SI, stimulated with OVA peptide
712 and IFNγ and TNFα production was quantified. Shown is the percentage of IFNγ⁺TNFα⁺
713 among OT-I cells. Data are pooled from 2-3 independent experiments (F, M, O-P) or

714 representative of 2 independent experiments (B, D, G-J, K, L, N) with n = 4-7 mice (B, D, F-
715 J, K, L, N) or with n = 8-10 samples (F, M, O-P), *p≤0.05, **p≤0.01, ***p≤0.001, unpaired t-
716 test. Bars represent the mean, symbols represent individual mice.

717 **RESOURCE AVAILABILITY**

718

719 **Lead contact**

720 Further information and requests for resources and reagents should be directed to and will be
721 fulfilled by Laura Mackay (lmackay@unimelb.edu.au) upon reasonable request.

722

723 **Materials availability**

724 Plasmids generated in this study are available from the lead contact upon request.

725

726 **Data and code availability**

727 All data have been deposited at GEO:GSExxxxx and are publicly available as of the date of
728 publication. Accession numbers are listed in the key resources table.

729 This paper does not report original code.

730 Any additional information required to reanalyse the data reported in this paper is available
731 from the lead contact upon request.

732

733 **EXPERIMENTAL MODEL AND SUBJECT DETAILS**

734

735 **Mice.** C57BL/6, B6.SJL-PtprcaPep3b/BoyJ (CD45.1), B6.SJL-PtprcaPep3b/BoyJ × C57BL/6
736 (CD45.1×CD45.2), P14 CD45.1, P14 *Zfp683*^{cre-tdTomato/+} × R26R-EYFP (P14 *Hobit*<sup>cre-
737 tdTomato</sup>:*Rosa26*^{LsL-YFP}), OT-I CD45.1, OT-I *Tbx21*^{-/-}, OT-I *Tgfbr2*^{ff}.dLck-cre CD45.1 (OT-I
738 *Tgfbr2*^{-/-}), OT-I *Tbx21*^{-/-}*Tgfbr2*^{-/-}, *Il15*^{-/-}, and *Hic1*^{Citrine/+} mice were bred in the Department of
739 Microbiology and Immunology. *Zfp683*^{cre-tdTomato/+} mice were generated by the Kallies lab and
740 will be described in detail elsewhere. Female mice were used for experiments at 6-20 weeks of
741 age. P14 mice express a transgenic T cell receptor recognizing the LCMV glycoprotein-derived
742 epitope GP₃₃₋₄₁. OT-I mice express a transgenic T cell receptor recognizing the ovalbumin
743 epitope OVA₂₅₇₋₂₆₄. James Cagney (JaCa) “dirty” mice were generated by Tri Giang Phan
744 (Garvan Institute of Medical Research) and Jenny Kingham (Australian BioResources) with
745 approval from the Garvan/St Vincent’s Animal Ethics Committee (#17_16 and 20_19). Briefly,
746 outbred wildtype mice were sourced from a public educational farm (Calmsley Hill City Farm).
747 To establish breeding pairs for the JaCa colony, mice were sprayed with a topical application
748 of Ivermectin (1g/ml) and 24 hours later were on continuous treatment with Fenbendazole
749 (150ppm) medicated feed to treat pinworms. Sentinel mice were screened by serology every
750 six months for Mouse hepatitis virus, Mouse parvovirus, Minute virus of mice, Mouse

751 norovirus, Theiler's encephalomyelitis virus and Rotavirus, and PCR on pooled faeces to detect
752 *Helicobacter spp.* fecal pellets were collected and stored at -80°C and processed in batches.
753 16s rRNA sequencing was performed to ensure the diversity and stability of the vertically
754 transmitted microbiota was maintained in the offsprings. For cohousing experiments, JaCa
755 female mice were cohoused with >12-weeks old female C57BL/6 for >30 days for horizontal
756 transmission of the microbiota. Age- and sex-matched C57BL/6 were maintained under SPF
757 conditions. All animal experiments were approved by the University of Melbourne Animal
758 Ethics Committee.

759

760 **T cell transfer.** For adoptive transfers of naive P14 or OT-I cells were carried out intravenously
761 (i.v.) with lymph node suspensions. Naive P14 or OT-I cells were transferred at a total number
762 of 5×10^4 or 2.5×10^4 cells/population in co-transfer experiments, where cell types were
763 transferred at a ratio of 1:1. For in vitro-activated T cell transfer, P14 or OT-I cells were
764 activated in culture for 4–5 d with GP₃₃₋₄₁ (KAVYNFATM) or OVA₂₅₇₋₂₆₄ (SIINFEKL)
765 peptide-pulsed splenocytes, respectively, in the presence of recombinant human IL-2 (25
766 U/mL; PeproTech), or with atRA (10 nM, Sigma Aldrich) at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. Cells were
767 transferred i.v. to naïve recipient mice at a total of $3.5-10 \times 10^6$ cells/population.

768

769 **Infections and DNFB treatment.** HSV infection was performed by scarification using 1×10^6
770 plaque forming units (pfu) of the KOS strain of the virus modified to express ovalbumin protein
771 (HSV-OVA)¹¹. LCMV-OVA (artLCMV) was obtained from Doron Merkler⁷⁶. LCMV
772 infection was performed by intraperitoneal (i.p.) injection of 2×10^5 pfu of the Armstrong strain
773 of LCMV or 10^5 pfu of the OVA strain of LCMV. Lm infection was performed through oral
774 feeding using a recombinant strain that carries OVA and a mutated internalin A. Mice were
775 infected with 10^9 cfu of Lm-OVA as described²⁶. For DNFB treatment, mice were shaved and
776 depilated before application of 15-20 µL of DNFB (0.25%) in acetone and oil (4:1) to a 1.5cm²
777 region of skin on the same day as activated T cell transfer or 3 days following LCMV infection.

778

779 **In vivo treatments.** Mice were injected intraperitoneally with DMSO, 5 mg/kg RARα/β
780 agonist AM80 (Sigma Aldrich), or 1 mg/kg pan-RAR antagonist AGN194310 every other day
781 for a week until euthanasia. To inhibit S1P-signaling pathways, mice were administered
782 FTY720 (Cayman Chemical) diluted in 2% (2-Hydroxypropyl)-β-cyclodextrin (Sigma-
783 Aldrich) or vehicle daily via i.p. injection (1µg/g) for a week until euthanasia. In all

784 experiments assessing SI T_{RM} cell maintenance after AGN194310 treatment, mice were
785 injected i.v. with 50µg of T_{REG}-protector (anti-ARTC2.2) nanobody (Biolegend) 30 min before
786 sacrifice to prevent P2RX7-mediated cell death during tissue-processing³⁹.

787

788 **Mouse tissue processing.** Spleen and lymph nodes were processed into a single-cell
789 suspension using metal meshes. Livers were meshed through 70µm cell strainers and pellets
790 were resuspended in 35% isotonic Percoll (GE Healthcare) prior to density gradient
791 centrifugation (500g, 20min). Spleen and liver red blood cells were lysed using 1X RBC lysis
792 buffer (eBioscience). SI was cleared of luminal contents and Peyer's patches were excised.
793 Intestines were longitudinally opened, cut into ~1cm fragments which were incubated at 37°C
794 for min with lateral rotation (230rpm) in 10% Hanks' balanced salt solution/HEPES containing
795 dithioerythritol (0.15mg/mL; Sigma Aldrich). Intra-epithelial lymphocytes were then purified
796 using a 44/70% Percoll gradient centrifugation. Flank skin was shaved and depilated and an
797 area of 1-3cm² was excised. Skin was incubated in Dispase II (2.5mg/mL; Roche) for 90min
798 at 37°C. Epidermal and dermal layers were separated, placed in Collagenase III (3mg/mL;
799 Worthington) and DNase I (5µg/mL; Roche), chopped into fine pieces and further incubated
800 for 30min at 37°C. Digested skin was homogenized into a single-cell suspension and
801 sequentially passed through 70µm and 30µm nylon mesh.

802

803 **Flow cytometry.**

804 Mouse cells were stained at 4°C for 60 min with the following antibodies (all purchased from
805 BD Bioscience, Biolegend or ThermoFisher): anti-B220 (RA3-6B2), anti-CD8α (53-6.7), anti-
806 CD8β (H35-17.2), anti-CD11a (M17/4), anti-CD11b (M1/70), anti-CD18 (M18/2), anti-CD38
807 (90), anti-CD39 (Y23-1185), anti-CD43 (S11), anti-CD44 (IM7), anti-CD45.1 (A20), anti-
808 CD45.2 (104), anti-CD45RB (16A), anti-CD49a (Ha31/8), anti-CD55 (RIKO-3), anti-CD62L
809 (MEL-14), anti-CD69 (H1.2F3), anti-CD73 (TY/11.8), anti-CD101 (Moushi101), anti-CD103
810 (2E7), anti-CD122 (5H4), anti-CD127 (A7R34), anti-CD218a (P3TUNYA), anti-CXCR3
811 (CXCR3-173), anti-CXCR6 (SA051D1), anti-CX3CR1 (SA011F11), anti-Integrinβ7 (FIB27),
812 anti-KLRG1 (2F1), anti-Ly6A/E (D7), anti-Ly6C (HK1.4), anti-MHCII (M5/114.15.2), anti-
813 NK1.1 (PK136), anti-NKG2D (CX5), anti-PD-1 (29F.1A12), anti-TCRβ (H57-597), anti-
814 TCRγδ (GL3), anti-Thy1.1 (OX-7), anti-Thy1.2 (53-2.1), anti-Vα2 (B20.1). For transcription
815 factor staining, cells were fixed and permeabilized using FoxP3 Transcription Factor staining
816 buffer set and stained with the following antibodies (all purchased from BD, Biolegend, Cell

817 Signaling or ThermoFisher): anti-Bcl2 (3F11), anti-Bim (C34C5), anti-Eomes (Dan11mag),
818 anti-FoxP3 (FJK-16s), anti-GATA3 (L50-823), anti-Ki67 (SolA15), anti-ROR γ t (Q31-378),
819 anti-Runx3 (R3-5G4), anti-Tbet (4B10) and anti-TCF1 (C63D9). Human cells were stained at
820 4°C for 60 min with the following antibodies (all purchased from BD Bioscience, Biolegend
821 or ThermoFisher): anti-CD8 α (HIT8a), anti-CD69 (FN50), anti-CD103 (Ber-ACT8). Dead
822 cells were excluded from analysis using DAPI (0.5 μ M; Biolegend), eFluor506, Zombie Yellow
823 or Zombie NIR fixable live/dead (Biolegend). For flow cytometry experiments, samples were
824 acquired on a 5-laser BD Fortessa X20 or 5-laser Cytex Aurora. For cell sorting experiments,
825 CD8⁺ T cells were enriched using a 5-laser BD FACS Aria III (BD Bioscience) or a 4-laser
826 Beckman Coulter Cytotflex SRT (>95% purity). Data was analysed on Flowjo v10 (Treestar)
827 or OMIQ (<https://www.omiq.ai/>).

828

829 **T cell stimulations and cytokine staining.** For the assessment of cytokine production *in vitro*,
830 single cell suspensions of processed tissues were cultured in complete RPMI in the presence
831 of GP₃₃₋₄₁ (KAVYNFATM) or OVA₂₅₇₋₂₆₄ (SIINFEKL) peptide, brefeldin A (10 μ g/mL;
832 Sigma-Aldrich), and P2RX7 inhibitor A-438079 (10 μ M, Santa Cruz Biotechnology) for 4h at
833 37°C. For intracellular staining, cells were processed using BD fixation and permeabilization
834 kit and stained with the following antibodies (all purchased from BD, Biolegend, or
835 ThermoFisher): GranzymeA (GzA-3G8.5), Granzyme B (QA16A02), IL-2 (JES6-5H4), IFN γ
836 (XMG1.2) and TNF α (MP6-XT22).

837

838 **Flow cytometry high dimensional analyses.** Flow cytometry data was scaled using
839 hyperbolic arcsine (asinh) transformation with OMIQ cloud platform (<https://www.omiq.ai/>).
840 UMAP dimensionality reduction was performed with OMIQ. One-SENSE analysis was
841 performed in R as described⁷⁷, with the exception that UMAP dimensionality reduction was
842 used instead of t-SNE. UMAP and one-SENSE plots were color coded in R using the *ggplot2*
843 package. Heatmaps and correlation plots were generated using asinh transformed median
844 expression in R using the *pheatmap* R package.

845

846 **Immunofluorescence and confocal microscopy.** SI was collected and fixed in 4% PFA for 4
847 h, washed in PBS and dehydrated in 30% sucrose (w/v in PBS) before being embedded in OCT
848 freezing medium. Tissue sections of 18 μ m thickness were cut using a cryostat (Leica
849 CM3050S) and air-dried before being fixed in ice-cold acetone for 5 min, dried and then

850 blocked for 45 min in PBS containing 2.5% goat serum 2.5% donkey serum at room
851 temperature. Sections were stained with primary antibody overnight at room temperature (anti-
852 Thy1.1-AlexaFluor647, anti-Lyve1-eFluor570, anti-EpCAM-biotin and anti-CollagenIV).
853 Slides were washed in PBS and stained with a Streptavidin-conjugated DyLight 800 and anti-
854 rabbit AlexaFluor 405 for 1 h at RT. Stained sections were mounted in ProLong Diamond
855 antifade reagent and images were acquired on a LSM980 spectral confocal microscope (Zeiss)
856 on a 40× oil (NA 1.4) objective using 405nm, 488nm, 561nm, 639nm and 730nm laser lines
857 via Online Fingerprinting mode. Images were spectrally unmixed through single-color
858 reference spectra, and Z-stacks were scanned at 1024×1024 pixel resolution and a 50% overlap.
859 Post-acquisition processing was performed by applying a Gaussian filter, residual spectral
860 spillover corrected using the Channel Arithmetics XT function and 3D surface rendering were
861 all performed in Imaris 9.3.1.

862

863 **Retinoic acid quantification.** Blood was collected and processed under dark conditions. SPF
864 mice were administered i.p. with 50mg/kg of atRA (Sigma-Aldrich) dissolved in cornoil 90
865 min before blood collection to serve as positive control. Serum was run on a retinoic acid
866 ELISA kit (MyBiosource, MBS706971) according to manufacturer instructions. Briefly,
867 samples were incubated with 50 ml HRP-conjugated antibody for 40 min at 37°C, washed 5
868 times with wash buffer, and incubated with TMB substrate for 20 min at 37°C. The reaction
869 was quenched, and absorbance was measured of each well using a micro-plate reader
870 (FLUOstar Omega, BMG Labtech) set to 450 nm with wavelength correction set to 540nm.

871

872 **CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing of CD8⁺ T cells.** sgRNA targeting *Cd19* (5'-
873 AAUGUCUCAGACCAUAUGGG-3' and 5'-GAGAAGCUGGCUUGGUAUCG-3'), *Hic1*
874 (5'-AGUGUGCGGAAAGCGCGGAG-3' and 5'-CUUGUGCGACGUGAUCaucg-3'),
875 *Itgae* (5'-GUCAUGGUGGUACUACUGA-3' and 5'-GAUUGCCUCAGACCCCAAAG-
876 3'), *P2rx7* (5'-UGAGCGAUAAAGCUGUACCAG-3' and 5'-
877 UAUCAGCUCCGUGCACACCA-3' or *Tbx21* (5'- UGAACUUGGACCACAACAGG-3'
878 and 5'-GCGGUACCAGAGCGGCAAGU-3'), were purchased from Synthego
879 (CRISPRevolution sgRNA EZ Kit). sgRNA/Cas9 RNP were formed by incubating 1μL of
880 sgRNA (0.3nmol/μL) with 0.6μL Alt-R S.p. Cas9 Nuclease V3 (10mg/mL; Integrated DNA
881 Technologies) for 10min at room temperature. Naïve T cells were resuspended in 20μL P3
882 buffer (P3 primary cell 4D-Nucleofector X Kit S; Lonza), mixed with sgRNA/Cas9 RNP and
883 electroporated using Lonza 4D-Nucleofector system (pulse code: DN100). Cells were rested

884 for 10 min at 37°C before i.v. transfer. 1×10^5 P14 or OT-I cells edited with control (*sgCdl9*)
885 and target guides were mixed at 1:1 ratio and were transferred intravenously. Mice receiving
886 edited naïve T cells were infected with LCMV 4 days following cell transfer.

887

888 **Retroviral transduction of CD8⁺ T cells.** Retroviruses were produced using Plat-E cells (Cell
889 Biolabs) which were transfected with pCL-Eco, pMSCV-IRES-GFP II (pMIG II) and pMSCV-
890 IRES-Ametrine II (pMIA II) based vectors. Plat-E cells were seeded in 96-mm dishes at a
891 density of 7×10^6 cells 12 hours before transfection with 14mg of pLMPd-Ametrine and 7mg
892 of pCL-Eco plasmid DNA using the CalPhos Mammalian Transfection kit (Takara). Viral
893 supernatants were harvested 48 hours later and filtered (0.45mm; Millipore). A truncated
894 version of human RAR α (RAR α 403)³² cDNA was cloned into pMIG II vector. Mouse *Ccr9*
895 cDNA was cloned into pMIA II vector. Purified naïve P14 CD8⁺ T cells were in vitro activated
896 with anti-CD3 (145-2C11) and anti-CD28 (37.51) (5mg/mL for each; both from BioXCell) for
897 24 hours and were “spinfected” with 0.5mL of retroviral supernatant in 24-well plates coated
898 with Retronectin (32mg/mL; Takara). CD8⁺ T cells were further expanded for 3 days in the
899 presence of IL-2 (25U/mL; Peprotech). Transduction efficiency was determined by Ametrine
900 or GFP expression. Cells transduced with EV-GFP and CCR9-Amt or EV-Amt and dnRAR α -
901 GFP retroviruses, and were mixed at 1:1 ratio. 2×10^5 transduced cells of the relevant specificity
902 were administered intravenously in mice that were infected with LCMV Armstrong or Lm-
903 OVA one day before.

904

905 **ATAC-seq.** WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells were isolated from the SI 8 d following LCMV-OVA
906 infection. CD69⁺ OT-I cells were sorted and cryopreserved in DMSO (10%). Frozen cells
907 were thawed and washed once in cold PBS. 70,000-200,000 cells were lysed using the 10x
908 single-cell ATAC lysis buffer and centrifuged for 10 min at 4°C/500g. Transposition reaction
909 was performed using Illumina Tagment DNA TDE1 Enzyme and Buffer Kits (FC-121-1030),
910 using 12.5 μ L 2x TD Buffer, 10.5 μ L H₂O, and 2 μ L transposase per reaction, and incubated
911 at 37°C for 30min. TE Buffer was added to halt the transposition reaction, then the product was
912 purified using Qiagen Minelute (28004). The elute underwent PCR using Phusion High-
913 Fidelity PCR MasterMix (NEB, M0531S) as follows; 5 min of initial extension at 72°C,
914 followed by 16 cycles of PCR (98°C/15s, 63°C/30s, 72°C/60s), followed by final extension
915 (72°C/3min). The resulting product was purified using AMPure XP Beads (A63881), eluted in
916 20 μ L H₂O, and quantified using a Quibit dsDNA HS Assay Kit (Invitrogen) and a High
917 Sensitivity DNA chip run on a Bioanalyzer 2100 system. The final product was sequenced on

918 a NovaSeq. For each bulk ATAC-seq library, adapters were trimmed, and fastq reads were
919 aligned using Bowtie2 to the *Mus musculus* reference genome (GRCm39/mm39). PCR
920 duplicates were removed such that only one representative read was selected per unique pair
921 of transposition events. Chromatin accessibility peaks were called using MACS2 using custom
922 parameters for ATAC-seq (nomodel, nolambda, keep-dup, all call-summits), and a signal track
923 in bdg form was emitted from the peak calling function that was subsequently converted into
924 a .bigwig for visualization with the SPMR flag. Across all chromatin accessibility samples, we
925 computed a consensus peak set and counts table using a previously described approach of
926 aggregating peak summits⁷⁸. Motif analyses were conducted using *chromVAR* and
927 *motifmatchR*. For the T-bet directed ChIP-seq data (SRA273724⁷⁹), fastq reads were aligned
928 using Bowtie2 to the *Mus musculus* reference genome (GRCm39/mm39) and were normalized
929 to the library size.

930

931 **RNA-seq.** To profile the transcriptome of effector CD8⁺ T cells cultured with RA and TGF- β ,
932 naive CD8⁺ T cells were enriched from spleen and lymph node suspension using CD8 EasySep
933 kit (StemCell Technologies) as per manufacturer's protocol. Enriched CD8⁺ T cells were
934 activated in 96-well plates coated with anti-CD3 and anti-CD28 (1mg/mL) and cultured in
935 complete RPMI (10% FCS, 200mM L-glutamine, 1M HEPES, PenStrep (10000U/mL
936 penicillin + 10000 μ g/mL streptomycin), 0.5mM β -mercaptoethanol) with IL-2 (10ng/mL), IL-
937 15 (10ng/mL) in the presence or absence of RA (10nM) and TGF- β (10ng/mL). mRNA was
938 isolated after 7 d using the RNeasy Micro kit (Qiagen). Samples were sequenced at Micromon
939 Genomics, Monash University. RNA quality was tested and samples were prepared using the
940 Illumina Truseq stranded mRNA sample preparation kit. Sequencing was then conducted on
941 MGI-2000RS with a PE 100bp cartridge. To profile the transcriptome of dnRAR α expressing
942 T_{RM} cells, congenically marked naïve P14 cells were activated and transduced with empty
943 (Ctrl-RV) or dnRAR α (dnRAR α -RV) retroviruses as shown above. Transduced cells were co-
944 transferred in LCMV-infected mice, and CD69⁺ T_{RM} cells from the liver and SI were sorted 14
945 d p.i. To profile the transcriptome of T_{RM} cells following RA signaling blockade, congenically
946 marked naïve P14 cells were transferred into LCMV-infected mice. At >30 d p.i., mice were
947 treated with DMSO or AGN194310 (RA antag.) every other day for 6 d and CD69⁺ P14 T_{RM}
948 cells were sorted from the liver and SI the following day. For both Ctrl and dnRAR α or DMSO
949 and RA antag, T_{RM} cell samples, mRNA was isolated using the RNAeasy Micro kit (Qiagen)
950 and was converted into cDNA using High Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit
951 (Thermofisher). Libraries were prepared using the SMART-seq HT Plus kit (Takara/Clontech)

952 according to manufacturer's instructions. Sequencing was then conducted at the WEHI
953 Advanced Genomics Hub on an Illumina NextSeq 2000. Data on Effector CD8⁺ T cell cultures
954 and RA antagonized SI T_{RM} cells were analyzed as follows: raw fastq files were processed
955 using the RNAsik pipeline⁸⁰, sequence reads were mapped to the *Mus musculus* genome
956 (GRCm38/mm10) using *STAR*, and reads mapping to Ensemble annotated genes were counted
957 with *featureCounts*. For the Mackay et al.¹³ (GSE70813) data, summarized raw counts were
958 downloaded from GEO, and HSV T_{EM} and T_{CM} cell spleen samples were treated as one group,
959 referred to as T_{CIRC} cells (HSV), and LCMV T_{EM} and T_{CM} cell samples were treated as one
960 group, referred to as T_{CIRC} cells (LCMV). For these data sets, genes without Entrez Gene IDs
961 were filtered, as were genes which failed to achieve a count above 10 in all samples in at least
962 one biological group. The Mackay data was further processed by filtering genes annotated as
963 'rRNA' and then applying the imputation strategy published previously^{17,81}. For these data sets,
964 counts-per-million (CPM) values were calculated, using scaling factors derived from the TMM
965 method⁸², then log₂ transformed with a prior count of 1, followed by application of the
966 normalization method *RUV-III*⁸³ with biological replicates nominated as replicates, mouse
967 housekeeping genes nominated as 'negative control' genes, and $k = 1$ factors of unwanted
968 variation. Normalization success was assessed with relative log expression plots⁸⁴, PCA
969 plots⁸⁵, and p-value histograms. The *edgeR* package was used to fit gene-wise negative
970 binomial generalized linear models for the experimental design with the output from *RUV-III*
971 as an additional model covariate, where the TMM scaling factors and a prior count of 1 were
972 used. Likelihood ratio tests were employed to test for differential expression (DE), where a
973 gene was judged to be differentially expressed if the Benjamini and Hochberg adjusted p-value
974 was less than 0.05. For the effector CD8⁺ T cell culture data, interaction was inferred using
975 the standard interaction contrast for a 2x2 factorial design. DE results for SI T_{RM} were obtained
976 by analysing Mackay SI T_{RM} and T_{CIRC} (LCMV) cell samples only, using the steps outlined
977 above. The core T_{RM} cell gene signature was obtained as described previously⁷⁵. logFC (log₂-
978 fold-change) and standardised logFC estimates, i.e. empirical Bayes moderated t-statistics,
979 were calculated by applying *limma* to TMM adjusted logCPM values, fitting gene-wise linear
980 models for the experimental design with the output from *RUV-III* as an additional model
981 covariate, where the 'trend' and 'robust' options were specified. Skin, liver, and SI logFCs
982 were derived from three separate analyses of the Mackay data, applying the steps outlined
983 above to the following samples: (1) skin T_{RM} and T_{CIRC} cells (HSV), (2) liver T_{RM} and T_{CIRC}
984 cells (LCMV); and (3) SI T_{RM} and T_{CIRC} cells (LCMV). Core T_{RM} cell signature logFCs were
985 calculated by averaging the logFC estimates obtained for skin, liver, and SI. For the dnRARα

986 T_{RM} cell data set, files were aligned to GRCm39/mm39 using *STAR*. Reads were mapped to
987 *Ensembl* annotated genes (GRCm39 Ensembl release 105) and counted using *featureCounts*.
988 Counts were loaded into *R* with samples grouped by tissue and genotype status. Genes were
989 filtered using *edgeR* ‘filterByExpr’ with a ‘min.count’ of 10 and ‘min.total.count’ of 15.
990 Normalization factors were calculated with the *edgeR* TMM method. Surrogate variable
991 analysis was used to remove unwanted noise and batch effects, using the *sva* package⁸⁶.
992 Surrogate variables were calculated with the ‘svaseq’ function using gene counts, a model
993 matrix constructed from the sample groups and a null model. *limma* ‘RemoveBatchEffects’
994 was applied to the log count-per-million and surrogate variables with PCA and MDS plots used
995 to evaluate and select a model with 4 surrogate variables. Statistics for association, i.e. log odds
996 ratios (LOR), were calculated by constructing a two-way contingency table counting the
997 number of genes with concordant/discordant logFCs, and p-values for association were
998 obtained by applying *Fisher’s exact test* to the table. Barcode enrichment plots were generated
999 using *limma*, and gene set enrichment p-values were calculated using the function *fry*.
1000 Heatmaps were produced from *RUV-III* normalized data, using gene-wise standardization,
1001 producing a Z-score, with genes clustered by Pearson correlation. UpSet plots were made with
1002 the package *UpSetR*.

1003

1004 **16S rRNA-seq.** Genomic DNA extraction and 16S rRNA gene amplicon library construction
1005 was performed following the Earth Microbiome Project protocols
1006 ([dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kqdg3dzzl25z/v2](https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kqdg3dzzl25z/v2)) and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq.
1007 Sequence data processing and microbiome profiling was performed using the *QIIME2* platform
1008 (v.2021.4.0). Specifically, quality filtering was performed using default cutoffs, Deblur was
1009 used for sub-operational OTU (sOTU) picking after trimming reads to 150bp, and taxonomic
1010 classification was performed using the sklearn-based classifier trained on the Greengenes 13_8
1011 16S database. All subsequent analyses were performed in *R* (v.4.2.3) using the *qiime2R*,
1012 *tidyverse*, *vegan*, *phyloseq*, and *ComplexHeatmap* libraries. sOTUs with a mean relative
1013 abundance < 0.1% in both mouse genotypes were removed from the dataset before further
1014 analysis. Between-sample (beta) diversity was calculated using the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity
1015 index on OTU-level data and visualized using Nonmetric Multidimensional Scaling.

1016

1017 **Statistical analysis.** Statistics analyses were calculated by performing unpaired or paired t-
1018 test, One-way ANOVA test with Tukey’s post-test using Prism 10 (GraphPad). *p < 0.05, **p
1019 < 0.01, ***p < 0.001, and ****p < 0.0001.

1020 **Video S1 (Related to Figure 6). SI T_{RM} cells are found associated with lymphatics after**
1021 **RA signaling blockade.** Mice received Thy1.1⁺ P14 cells and were infected with LCMV. At
1022 >30 d p.i., mice were treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or AGN194310 (RA antag.) for 6 d, and were
1023 sacrificed the following day. 3D-rendered video from confocal microscopy images of SI
1024 showing lymphatic endothelium (LyVE-1, *red*), P14 cells (Thy1.1, *green*) and epithelium
1025 (EpCAM, *blue*) in Ctrl and RA antag. treated mice. Data are representative of 2 independent
1026 experiments with n = 5 mice per group.
1027

1028 **References**

1029

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Figure S1 (Related to Figure 1)

Figure S1 (Related to Figure 1) CD8⁺ T_{RM} cells engage an alternative RA developmental axis in the absence of T-bet. (A) WT or *I15*^{-/-} mice received CD45.1⁺ P14 cells and were infected with LCMV and treated with DNFB. CD69⁺ P14 T_{RM} cell numbers from indicated organs >30 d p.i. (B) Congenically distinct naïve WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells were co-transferred into LCMV-OVA infected mice. Quantification of CD103 expression in SI WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells at indicated time points. (C-E) Naïve WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells were edited using CD19-targeting (*sgCd19*) or CD103-targeting (*sgltgae*) sgRNA/Cas9 RNPs and co-transferred into LCMV-OVA infected mice. (D) CD103 expression and (E) numbers of SI CD69⁺ OT-I T_{RM} cells >30 d p.i. for indicated genotypes. (F-G) WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I T cells were primed with LCMV-OVA. SI CD69⁺ OT-I cells were sort-purified 8 d p.i. and subjected to ATAC-seq (see Figure 1J) (F) chromVAR motif accessibility heatmap for indicated motifs and (G) genome tracks of selected gene loci in WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells. (H) Reactome pathway analysis of genes with differentially accessible chromatin regions (DACR) enriched in *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells. (I) Volcano plot showing peak deviation derived from *Rara*, *Rarg*, *Rxra*, *Rxrb* and *Hic1* loci with DACR between WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells. (J) Genome track of indicated loci in SI WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells (*top*) and from T-bet ChIP-seq performed on spleen effector P14 cells isolated 8 d post-LCMV (*bottom*) (SRA273724⁷⁵). (K) Effector WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells were cultured in the presence of RA for 4 d, and expression of $\alpha 4\beta 7$ and CCR9 was quantified. (L) Effector *Hic1*^{Citrine/+} CD8⁺ T cells were edited with *sgCd19* or T-bet-targeting (*sgTbx21*) sgRNA/Cas9 RNPs, cultured in the presence of RA for 4 d, and expression of *Hic1* was quantified. (M) Effector WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells were co-transferred into naïve mice that were treated with DMSO (Ctrl), AM80 (RA ag.) or AGN194310 (RA antag.) from 0 to 6 d post-transfer. SI OT-I cells were isolated 30 d post-transfer. Shown are frequencies of WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells for indicated treatments. (N) P14 cells were transduced with empty (Ctrl-RV) or dnRAR α (dnRAR α -RV) retroviruses and cultured in the presence or absence of RA for 4 d. Shown expression of $\alpha 4\beta 7$ and CCR9 for indicated genotypes. (O-P) Naïve WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells were edited using *sgCd19* or *Hic1*-targeting (*sgHic1*) sgRNA/Cas9 RNPs and co-transferred into LCMV-OVA infected mice as depicted in (O). (P) SI CD69⁺ OT-I T_{RM} cells numbers and (Q) ratios of WT and *Tbx21*^{-/-} OT-I cells >30 d p.i. for indicated genotypes. Data are pooled from 2-3 independent experiments (A-E, M) or representative of 1-3 independent experiments (B, D, K-L, P-Q) with n = 7-15 (A-E, M, P-Q) mice per group or n = 2-3 samples (K-L, N). *p \leq 0.05, **p \leq 0.01, ***p \leq 0.001, ****p \leq 0.0001, n.s. = non significant, unpaired t-test (A, K-L, P-Q), ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparisons test (E). Bars represent the mean; symbols represent individual mice.

Figure S2 (Related to Figure 2)

Figure S2 (Related to Figure 2) CD8⁺ T cells require RAR α to establish tissue residency in the liver, SI and kidney. (A-D) P14 cells were transduced with either empty (Ctrl-RV) or dnRAR α (dnRAR α -RV) retroviruses, co-transferred into LCMV infected recipient mice and isolated from indicated tissues 8 d p.i., as depicted in (A). (B) Numbers of transduced KLRG1⁺CD127⁺ (memory precursor effector cell [MPEC]) and KLRG1⁺CD127⁻ (short-lived effector cell [SLEC]) P14 cells from indicated tissues and (C) CD69⁺ P14 cells from indicated tissues. (D) Ratio of Ctrl and dnRAR α P14 cells in indicated tissues. (E-H) P14 cells were transduced with Ctrl-RV or dnRAR α -RV, co-transferred into LCMV infected recipient mice and isolated from indicated tissues 21 d p.i., as depicted in (E). (F) Numbers of transduced P14 cells (*spleen*) and CD69⁺ P14 T_{RM} cells from indicated tissues. (G) Ratio of Ctrl and dnRAR α P14 cells in indicated tissues. (H-J) OT-I cells were transduced with Ctrl-RV or dnRAR α -RV, co-transferred into Lm-OVA infected recipient mice and isolated from indicated tissues 21 d p.i., as depicted in (H). (I) Numbers of transduced OT-I cells (*spleen*) and CD69⁺ P14 T_{RM} cells from indicated tissues. (J) Ratio of Ctrl and dnRAR α P14 cells in indicated tissues. (K-M) Congenically marked naïve P14 cells were edited using CD19-targeting (*sgCd19*) or *Hic1*-targeting (*sgHic1*) sgRNA/Cas9 RNPs. P14 cells were co-transferred into LCMV infected, DNFB-treated recipient mice and isolated from the indicated tissues >30 d p.i. as depicted in (K). (L) Numbers of CD69⁺ P14 T_{RM} cells and (M) ratio of *sgHic1* and *sgCd19* P14 cells in indicated tissues. (N) Congenically distinct effector WT and *Tgfbr2*^{-/-} OT-I cells were co-transferred into naïve recipients. Mice were treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or AM80 (RA ag.) from 0 to 6 d post-transfer and OT-I cells isolated from the SI 30 d post-transfer. Shown are flow cytometry plots showing expression of CD69 and CD103 expression. (O-P) Congenically distinct effector WT and *Tgfbr2*^{-/-} OT-I cells were transduced with either empty (Ctrl-RV) or CCR9 (CCR9-RV) retroviruses, co-transferred into naïve recipient mice, as depicted in (O). (P) Shown are numbers of transduced WT and *Tgfbr2*^{-/-} OT-I cells isolated 7 d p.i. from the SI. Data are pooled from two independent experiments (A-J, N-P) or representative of two independent experiments (L-M) with n = 6-16 mice per group. *p \leq 0.05, **p \leq 0.01, ***p \leq 0.001, ****p \leq 0.0001, n.s. = non significant, paired t-test (B-C, F, J, O). or unpaired t-test (N) or ordinary one-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparisons test (D, G, K). Bars represent the mean; symbols represent individual mice.

Figure S3 (Related to Figure 3)

Figure S3 (Related to Figure 3) RA and TGF- β regulate tissue-specific transcriptional programs of T_{RM} cells. **(A)** Effector CD8⁺ T cells were cultured in the absence (Ctrl) or presence of TGF- β , RA or RA+TGF- β for 7 d and subjected to RNA-seq. **(A)** Gene expression data from cultured CD8⁺ T cells was compared to skin, liver and SI T_{RM} cells transcriptional signatures from GSE70813¹³. Shown are heatmaps displaying top 20 DEGs of TGF β - versus Ctrl-cultured cells (*left panel*) (FDR \leq 0.01; logFC \geq 1) that were DEGs in skin and SI but not liver T_{RM} cells versus T_{CIRC} cells; and top 20 DEGs of RA- versus Ctrl-cultured cells (*right panel*) (FDR \leq 0.01; logFC \geq 1) that were DEGs in liver and SI but not skin T_{RM} cells. **(B-C)** P14 Cells were transduced with either empty (Ctrl-RV) or dnRAR α (dnRAR α -RV) retroviruses, and co-transferred into LCMV infected recipient mice. CD69⁺ transduced P14 T_{RM} cells were sorted from indicated tissues 14 d p.i., and subjected to bulk RNA-seq. **(B)** Volcano plots displaying DEGs between dnRAR α versus Ctrl CD69⁺ P14 T_{RM} cells from indicated tissues. Colored points indicate average logFC > 0.2 and P < 0.05 upregulated (*red*) or downregulated (*blue*) in dnRAR α versus Ctrl CD69⁺ P14 T_{RM} cells. **(C)** Gene Ontology (GO) biological process analysis of DEGs (P < 0.01) in dnRAR α versus Ctrl CD69⁺ P14 T_{RM} cells from indicated tissues. **(D)** Effector CD8⁺ T cells were cultured in the absence (Ctrl) or presence of TGF- β , RA or RA+TGF- β for 7 d and subjected to RNA-seq. Gene expression data from cultured CD8⁺ T cells was compared to SI T_{RM} cells transcriptional signatures from GSE70813¹³. Expression of indicated genes from TGF- β (*orange*), RA (*green*) or RA+TGF- β (*blue*) cultured cells versus Ctrl cells (*grey*). Data are representative of 2 independent experiments with n = 2-3 samples (A, D) or n = 4 samples (B-C).

Figures S4 (Related to Figure 4)

Figure S4 (Related to Figure 4) RA and TGF- β signals regulate the core transcriptional program of T_{RM} cells. (A) Effector CD8⁺ T cells were cultured in the absence (Ctrl) or presence of TGF- β , RA or RA+TGF- β for 7 d and subjected to RNA-seq. Shown are barcode enrichment plots showing expression changes induced by TGF- β , RA or RA+TGF- β in comparison to Ctrl for core T_{RM} signature genes derived from GSE70813¹³. (B-E) Naïve OT-I cells were primed with LCMV-OVA and isolated from the spleen and SI >30 d p.i. or effector OT-I cells were cultured in the absence (Ctrl) or presence of RA+TGF- β for 7 d. OT-I cells were analyzed by spectral cytometry with n=31 markers, as depicted in (B). (C) one-SENSE analysis using residency- or circulation-associated markers, depicting Ctrl (*light grey*), RA+TGF- β (*light green*), spleen T_{CIRC} (*dark grey*) and SI T_{RM} (*dark green*) OT-I cells. (D) Heatmap of differentially expressed markers in indicated populations. (E) Correlation matrix based on median expression profiles for indicated populations. Data are representative of 2 independent experiments with n = 2-3 samples (A) per group or n = 5 mice per group (B-E).

Figure S5 (Related to Figure 5)

Figure S5 (Related to Figure 5) RA signals modulate the differentiation of SI T_{RM} cells. **(A-C)** Mice received congenically marked P14 cells and were infected with LCMV. At 4 d p.i., mice were treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or AGN194310 (RA antag.) for 7 d and isolated from the SI >30 d p.i. **(B-C)** Numbers of **(B)** spleen and **(C)** SI P14 T cell populations for indicated treatments. **(D-F)** Mice received congenically marked effector OT-I cells were treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or AM80 (RA ag.) for 7 d, and isolated from the SI >30 d p.i. **(E-F)** Numbers of **(E)** spleen and **(F)** SI OT-I T cell populations for indicated treatments. Data are pooled from 2 independent experiments (D-F) or representative of 2 independent experiments (A-C) with n = 4-5 (A-C), or n = 9-10 (D-F) mice per group, *p≤0.05, **p≤0.01, ***p≤0.001, ****p≤0.0001, n.s. = non significant, unpaired t-test. Bars represent the mean; symbols represent individual mice.

Figure S6 (Related to Figure 6)

Figure S6 (Related to Figure 6) RA signals modulate the maintenance of SI T_{RM} cells. (A-B) Mice received congenically marked P14 cells and were infected with LCMV. At >30 d p.i., mice were treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or AGN194310 (RA antag.) for 6 d and CD69⁺ T_{RM} cells were isolated from the SI the following day and subjected to bulk RNA-seq, as depicted in **(A)**. **(B)** Volcano plot displaying DEGs between P14 T_{RM} cells isolated from RA antag-treated versus Ctrl mice. Colored points indicate average logFC > 0.2 and P < 0.05 up (*red*) and down (*blue*) in SI T_{RM} cells isolated from RA antag-treated versus Ctrl mice or not differentially expressed (*grey*). Lines indicate apoptosis regulators. **(C-D)** Mice received congenically marked P14 cells and were infected with LCMV. At >30 d p.i., mice were treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or AGN194310 (RA antag.) for 6 d and P14 cells were isolated from indicated organs. **(C)** Expression of Bcl2, Bim, Ki-67 and **(D)** P2RX7 was quantified in P14 cells in indicated organs. **(E-G)** Congenically distinct P14 cells were edited using CD19-targeting (*sgCd19*) or P2RX7-targeting (*sgP2rx7*) sgRNA/Cas9 RNPs and co-transferred into LCMV infected mice, as depicted in **(E)**. **(F)** Representative flow cytometry plot of P2RX7 expression for indicated conditions. **(G)** CRISPR/Cas9-edited P14 cells were enumerated from the SI >30 d p.i. for indicated treatments. **(H)** Mice received congenically marked P14 *Hobit*^{cre-tdTom}:*Rosa26*^{LsL-YFP} cells and were infected with LCMV. At >30 d p.i., mice were treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or AGN194310 (RA antag.) for 6 d and isolated from indicated tissues the following day. Flow cytometry plots showing the frequency of Hobit-tdTom and YFP expression in P14 cells isolated from indicated organs and conditions. **(I-K)** Mice received congenically marked P14 cells and were infected with LCMV. At >30 d p.i., mice were treated with DMSO (Ctrl) or AGN194310 (RA antag.) for 6 d, while receiving FTY720 or Cyclodextran (Ctrl) daily before P14 cells were isolated from indicated organs at 7 d post treatment. **(I-J)** Enumeration of SI and mLN or **(K)** blood P14 T cell populations for indicated conditions. Data are pooled from 2-3 independent experiments (C, I-J) or representative of 1-3 independent experiments (B, D-H, K) with n = 4-8 mice per group, or n = 3 samples per group (B), *p≤0.05, **p≤0.01, ***p≤0.001, ****p≤0.0001, n.s. = non significant, unpaired t-test. Bars represent the mean; symbols represent individual mice.

Figure S7 (Related to Figure 7)

Figure S7 (Related to Figure 7). Effects of microbial diversity and RA-imprinting on T_{RM} cell phenotype and function. (A-B) Naïve C57BL/6 mice were housed in SPF conditions or cohoused with 'dirty' mice for >30 d. **(A)** PCA analysis comparing bacteria taxa identified by fecal 16S rRNA analysis between indicated groups. **(B)** Heatmap showing the last known bacteria taxa with greatest variance among groups. **(C-E)** Mice were housed in SPF conditions or cohoused with 'dirty' mice for >30 d. **(C)** Shown is frequency of *Lactobacillus* spp. determined by fecal 16S rRNA analysis. **(D)** Shown are numbers (*left*) and expression of CD44 and CD62L (*right*) of CD8⁺CD44^{hi} cells isolated from the blood from SPF or cohoused mice. **(E)** Shown is fold-change of the number of indicated immune cell populations from cohoused and SPF mice isolated at >30 days post cohousing. **(F-H)** P14 cells were transduced with either empty (Ctrl-RV) or dnRAR α (dnRAR α -RV) retroviruses, co-transferred into LCMV infected recipient mice and isolated from indicated tissues 21 d p.i., as depicted in **(F)**. P14 cells were isolated from the SI and liver, stimulated with GP₃₃₋₄₁ peptide and IFN γ and TNF α production was quantified. **(G-H)** Shown is the percentage of IFN γ ⁺TNF α ⁺ among Ctrl or dnRAR α transduced P14 T_{RM} cells. **(I-K)** Congenically distinct effector OT-I cells were cultured in the absence (-RA) or presence (+RA) of RA, transferred into recipient mice and isolated from indicated tissues 30 d later, as depicted in **(I)**. OT-I cells were isolated from the SI and liver, stimulated with OVA peptide and IFN γ and TNF α production was quantified. **(J-K)** Shown is the percentage of IFN γ ⁺TNF α ⁺ among OT-I cells. Data are representative of 1-3 independent experiments or pooled from two independent experiments (G-H) with n = 3-10 (A-B, C-E, G-H) samples or n = 5 mice per group (J-K), *p \leq 0.05, ****p \leq 0.0001, PERMANOVA test (A) or unpaired t-test (C-J). Bars represent the mean, symbols represent individual mice.

Table S1. List of SI T_{RM} genes uniquely regulated by RA+TGF- β (Related to Figure 3).

Up genes (exclusive to RA+TGF- β)	Down genes (exclusive to RA+TGF- β)
<i>Abhd12</i>	<i>Abcc4</i>
<i>Abhd4</i>	<i>Add1</i>
<i>Akr1a1</i>	<i>AI413582</i>
<i>Akr1b7</i>	<i>Ankib1</i>
<i>Avil</i>	<i>Ankrd29</i>
<i>Ccl3</i>	<i>Ankrd44</i>
<i>Ccl4</i>	<i>Ar</i>
<i>Cd69</i>	<i>Aven</i>
<i>Cd72</i>	<i>B230219D22Rik</i>
<i>Cebpd</i>	<i>Birc6</i>
<i>Chid1</i>	<i>Ccne1</i>
<i>Cipc</i>	<i>Crybg3</i>
<i>Csrp2</i>	<i>Dennd4c</i>
<i>Ctnnbip1</i>	<i>Dpy19l1</i>
<i>Ddit3</i>	<i>Fam171b</i>
<i>Ddx58</i>	<i>Far1</i>
<i>Decr1</i>	<i>Fbxo27</i>
<i>Dtx1</i>	<i>Frrs1</i>
<i>Efnb1</i>	<i>G430095P16Rik</i>
<i>Egr1</i>	<i>Galnt9</i>
<i>Esrra</i>	<i>Gm2a</i>
<i>Fbxw9</i>	<i>H2-Oa</i>
<i>Fgl2</i>	<i>Il2rb</i>
<i>Gng12</i>	<i>Kctd10</i>
<i>Gpr18</i>	<i>Kif5c</i>
<i>Haus3</i>	<i>Klf12</i>
<i>Hs1bp3</i>	<i>Klf8</i>
<i>Hsd3b7</i>	<i>Kmt2a</i>
<i>Isg15</i>	<i>Kmt2d</i>
<i>Khk</i>	<i>Kremen2</i>
<i>Klc4</i>	<i>Lactb</i>
<i>Ktn1</i>	<i>Lrrc75b</i>
<i>Lig1</i>	<i>Lsp1</i>
<i>Maik</i>	<i>Malt1</i>
<i>Mob3c</i>	<i>Maml2</i>
<i>N4bp2l1</i>	<i>Mtmr14</i>
<i>Nadsyn1</i>	<i>Myo1g</i>
<i>Nfxl1</i>	<i>Nebi</i>
<i>Nudt1</i>	<i>Ogt</i>
<i>Pde7a</i>	<i>Pafah1b1</i>
<i>Pef1</i>	<i>Parp3</i>
<i>Pex16</i>	<i>Pglyrp1</i>
<i>Pgap3</i>	<i>Poglut1</i>
<i>Pla2g3</i>	<i>Polm</i>
<i>Pmpcb</i>	<i>Prdm5</i>
<i>Ptger4</i>	<i>Rab39b</i>
<i>Ptov1</i>	<i>Rabgap1l</i>
<i>R3hdm2</i>	<i>Rmnd5a</i>
<i>Rapsn</i>	<i>Sgms1</i>
<i>Rbks</i>	<i>Sh3bp1</i>
<i>Scamp1</i>	<i>Skida1</i>
<i>Sec11c</i>	<i>Sptan1</i>
<i>Slc46a1</i>	<i>Stk4</i>
<i>Soat2</i>	<i>Syng3</i>
<i>Sod1</i>	<i>Tg</i>
<i>Sphk2</i>	<i>Tmem106b</i>

<i>Tbc1d8</i>	<i>Tnfrsf22</i>
<i>Tmem86a</i>	<i>Trp73</i>
<i>Trappc2l</i>	<i>Usp31</i>
<i>Trim14</i>	<i>Usp34</i>
<i>Txlng</i>	<i>Yeats4</i>
<i>Uqcrq</i>	<i>Zfp160</i>
	<i>Zfp386</i>
	<i>Zfp7</i>